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18th International Ichnofabric Workshop: New trends in ichnofabric analysis

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Trace fossil assemblages of the Devonian Imperial Formation: A comparative analysis with other Devonian studies

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This study focuses on the Devonian Imperial Formation, an Upper Devonian unit in the Northwest Territories (NWT) of Canada. Hitherto now, very little research has been conducted on this formation. However, it ostensibly spans the Frasnian-Famennian extinction level and stands to be a useful comparator to other Devonian locales. Using outcroppings from 4 locales in the Mackenzie Mountains of the NWT, we establish recurring trace fossil and sedimentary facies associations that are compared to other Devonian formations. The ichnological and sedimentological characteristics of the Imperial Formation are presented by facies association (FA) below.

Lower shoreface to offshore deposits (FA1) contain trace fossil assemblages characterized by high diversity in deposits showing high (3-5) ichnofabric indices. These assemblages predominantly feature deposit-feeding ichnofossils like *Cruziana* isp., *Planolites* isp., and *Phycosiphon* isp.

Inner shelf turbidite deposits (FA2) present moderate trace fossil diversity with assemblages including *Chondrites* isp., *Didymaulichnus* isp., *Oldhamia* isp., *Paleodictyon* isp., *Palaeophycus* isp., *Planolites* isp., *Psammichnites* isp., *Teichichnus* isp., *Thalassinoides* isp. Ichnofabric Index ranges from 1 to 4.

The deep marine turbidite deposits (FA3) show minimal, sporadically distributed bioturbation including the trace fossils *Arenicolites* isp., *Planolites* isp., *Chondrites* isp., and *Palaeophycus* isp., with no evidence of graphoglyptids (farming traces).

The observed trace fossil assemblages are shaped by varying physicochemical factors such as hydraulic energy, oxygen levels, and nutrient input. Comparative studies with other Devonian formations reveal the influence of paleogeographic context and tectonism on these trace fossil communities: (1) the lower shoreface to offshore is consistent with trace fossil assemblages from other Devonian shallow marine settings; (2) the inner shelf deposits present a higher diversity and abundance of trace fossils than reported in other Devonian studies, likely driven by its tropical paleogeographic location, which offered robust nutrient supplies and a greater variety of ecological niches, coupled with potentially higher oxygen levels at the seafloor; and

(3) some other Devonian turbidites are characterized by graphoglyptid. This absence suggests persistently high sedimentation rates and strong hydraulic-energy restricted infaunal colonization.

There is no stratigraphic level observed that would be indicative of a Frasnian-Famnenian extinction event; however, relative and absolute age are poorly constrained in the studied outcrops, severely limiting the potential for identifying this boundary.

Keywords: *ichnodiversity; trace fossil suites; paleoenvironment; shelf; Devonian.*

Table 1. Abundances of trace fossils documented from different stratigraphic sections of the Imperial River Formation.

Trace Fossils	<i>Arenicolites</i> isp.	<i>Asterosoma rudiciform</i>	<i>Bergueria perata</i>	<i>Chondrites intricatus</i>	<i>Cruziana</i> isp.	<i>Didymaulichnus lyelli</i>	<i>Diplichnites</i> isp.	<i>Lockeia siliquaria</i>	<i>Bromleyia magnifica</i>	<i>Oldhamia radiata</i>	<i>Paleodictyon imperfectum</i>	<i>Palaeophycus tubuaris</i>	<i>Phycosiphon incertum</i>	<i>Planolites</i> isp.	<i>Protovirgularia pennata</i>	<i>Psammichnites gigas</i>	<i>Rhizocorallium commune</i>	<i>Teichichnus zigzag</i>	<i>Thalassinoides horizontalis</i>	<i>Thalassinoides</i> isp.
Imperial River Section higher	abundant		abundant	abundant	abundant		average	abundant				abundant	abundant	average						
Imperial River Section lower				average		abundant		average			average	abundant		abundant		average				
Powell Creek Section higher	abundant			abundant	abundant							average		abundant			average			abundant
Powell Creek Section lower	average			average								average		abundant						
Carcajou Section higher	abundant	average		abundant								average	abundant	abundant						
Carcajou Section lower				average						average		abundant		abundant				average	average	

Trace fossil abundance color index	
abundant	abundant
average	average
rare	rare
not observed	not observed

Trace fossils in supratidal deposits of the Teresina Formation (Paraná Basin)

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The Teresina Formation (Upper Permian) in Prudentópolis, Paraná Basin, Brazil, comprises flaser- and wavy-bedded strata, and fine sandstone measures. This study examines the ichnoassemblage of supratidal deposits and interprets their paleoenvironmental and depositional dynamics. Six trace fossils were identified: *Skolithos* (*Glossifungites*), *Palaeophycus*, *Taenidium*, *Beaconites*, *Asterosoma*, and *Phycosiphon*. Simple vertical burrows (*Skolithos*) dominate flaser-bedded facies that are associated with mudcracks; subordinate traces include horizontal burrows with meniscate backfill (*Beaconites*) and smooth-walled horizontal burrows (*Palaeophycus*). In the wavy bedded deposits, firmground *Skolithos* also predominates, with less common traces including small, horizontally concentric-filled burrows (*Asterosoma*), sinuous structures with discrete spreiten (*Phycosiphon*), and meniscate-filled horizontal burrows (*Taenidium*). Three ichnocoenoses were identified. The softground *Asterosoma* ichnocoenosis, dominated by *Palaeophycus*, *Asterosoma*, and *Phycosiphon*, is restricted to two intervals of wavy bedded facies devoid of mudcracks. The softground pre-desiccation *Beaconites* ichnocoenosis, characterized by *Taenidium*, *Palaeophycus*, and *Beaconites*, reflects early colonization of softground substrates. The firmground post-desiccation *Glossifungites* ichnocoenosis, defined by *Skolithos*, represents colonization of firmgrounds preserved in a *Glossifungites* ichnofabric. These ichnocoenoses reveal episodic energy variations in intertidal and supratidal zones. The *Asterosoma* ichnocoenosis associated with the lithofacies characterizes intertidal environments, whereas the *Beaconites* and *Glossifungites* ichnocoenoses are indicative of supratidal settings. In this context, the *Glossifungites* ichnofabric is interpreted as autogenic, consistent with firmground formation in supratidal zones. These findings expand the ichnological record of the Teresina Formation, which was previously limited to subaqueous colonization in marine and deltaic settings.

Keywords: *supratidal deposits; Taenidium; autogenic Glossifungites; firmground; Permian.*

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Fig. 1. Geologic log of the studied outcrop in Prudentópolis (PR, Brazil).

Eifelian-Givetian invertebrate ichnoassemblages from Hamar Laghdad (Eastern Anti-Atlas, Morocco): ethological and palaeoenvironmental implication

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Herein, we describe invertebrate ichnofauna from Hamar Laghdad in Tafilalt Basin of Morocco, which occurs in Middle Devonian marly limestone layers of varying sand content and degree of dolomitization. More than 200 specimens, preserved in concave and/or convex epirelief were analysed. We distinguished two ichnoassemblages, (i) an Eifelian ichnoassemblage consisting of *Arenicolites* isp., *Crescentichnus* cf. *antarcticus*, *Selenichnites hundalensis*, (ii) and a Givetian ichnoassemblage containing *Arenicolites* isp., *Diplocraterion* isp., *Sinusichnus sinuosus*, *Thalassinoides paradoxicus*. *Crescentichnus* cf., *antarcticus* and *Selenichnites hundalensis* are commonly referred to fodinichnia of xiphosurans or trilobites, *Arenicolites* isp. and *Diplocraterion* isp. to suspension feeding and a dwelling behaviour of polychaete worms and crustaceans, *Sinusichnus sinuosus* and *Thalassinoides paradoxicus* to deposit-feeder non-decapod crustacean, and deposit-feeding and dwelling of crustacean. We presume that the Eifelian ichnoassemblage-bearing strata has been deposited in inner shelf environment with shallow water, high energy and abundant food. The Givetian ichnofossil-bearing strata were laid down in a relatively deeper inner shelf environment within high-energy settings and organic matter-rich substrate. Here we report the oldest occurrence of *Selenichnites* and *Sinusichnus* in Africa, and one of the oldest in the global record. These findings open possibilities of an ancient root for the represented complex behaviour of arthropods. Hamar Laghdad is renowned for its great palaeobiodiversity, which is most likely related to the local occurrence of a favourable environmental setting, characterised by a temporally and spatially varying topography formed by several cold and hydrothermal seeps. It is assumed that these conditions were created by sea-level fluctuations, currents and nutrient availability. The abundance and diversity of body- and trace fossils strongly encourages further systematic prospecting in Hamar Laghdad.

Keywords: invertebrate ichnofauna; Eifelian-Givetian; Hamar laghdad; Xiphosauran; *Sinusichnus*.

The ichnofabric approach: uses, misuses, and abuses

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Since its proposal in mid-eighties (Ekdale and Bromley, 1983; Bromley and Ekdale, 1986), the ichnofabric concept has attracted significant attention and ichnologists have aligned themselves as defenders or detractors. However, a significant number of papers adopting this approach have been published. Interestingly, as is the case of ichnofacies, the ichnofabric concept has been frequently misunderstood and its full potential has not been realized yet. The notion of ichnofabric is better understood as an approach that combines a series of related concepts which may be seen as elements of a toolbox. This approach has been particularly valuable to extract paleoecologic information at community level and to unravel the taphonomic overprint, avoiding a naïve reading of the fossil record.

Differentiating between simple ichnofabrics (i.e. those that result from the activity of a single endobenthic community at a given moment and are, therefore, the product of a single bioturbation or bioerosion event) and composite ichnofabrics (i.e. those produced by the replacement of successive communities or by the upward migration of a tiered community) remains essential (Bromley and Ekdale, 1986). We note that these distinction does not coincide with monospecific and plurispecific ichnofabrics. For example, simultaneous colonization of an event layer by more than one producer may result in a plurispecific simple ichnofabric. Colonization of a tempestite by a low-diversity opportunistic fauna producing *Skolithos* and *Arenicolites* illustrates this situation. Conversely, the upward relocation of a monospecific ichnocoenosis may result in the formation of a composite ichnofabric (i.e. a palimpsest). Examples of the latter are common in the stratigraphic record (e.g. many *Skolithos* assemblages), and they should not be confused with simple ichnofabrics.

Identifying the colonization surface associated with each bioturbation or bioerosion event is of paramount importance in the analysis of composite ichnofabrics. This may not always be possible, particularly in the case on long-lived communities. However, detecting changes in community composition or subtle discontinuities is crucial to unravel the depositional history of the sedimentary unit and its associated environmental significance. The classification of composite ichnofabrics into autocomposite (i.e. gradual upward migration of tiered communities keeping pace with sedimentation), heterocomposite (i.e. more than one ichnocoenosis formed in response to short- to medium-term environmental perturbations within

a depositional system), and ultracomposite (i.e. overprinting of ichnocoenoses that are significantly temporally disjunct and result from bioturbation in more than one depositional system; emplacements separated by up to 10^6 to 10^8 yr) represents a useful addition to the conceptual framework of the ichnofabric approach (Savrda, 2016).

Assessing intensity of bioturbation is just one of the components in the ichnofabric approach, which in early studies was given unjustified pre-eminence. The ichnofabric approach works as its best when seen in a holistic fashion, considering its multiple related components such as tiering and ichnoguilds, which help to reconstruct niche partitioning and community dynamics. Similarly, the fact that both discrete biogenic structures and undetermined biogenic mottling were considered in the ichnofabric approach resulted in the misleading notion that there was little room for ichnotaxonomic determinations in ichnofabric analysis. Probably too much energy was spent in placing the ichnofabric approach in opposition to the ichnofacies model. At present both are seen as integral parts of the ichnologic analysis toolbox, influencing and complementing each other. Interpretation of ichnofabrics benefits from the predictive strength of the ichnofacies model, and new ichnofacies have been proposed or redefined (e.g., *Trypanites* and *Gnathichnus*) that take into consideration tools that are typically associated with the ichnofabric approach (Bromley and Asgaard, 1993). Additionally, ichnofabrics analysis allows to detect profound synecologic changes at community scale and reveals a more temporally dynamic picture of ichnofacies at the macroevolutionary scale.

Keywords: *ichnofabric; tiering; ichnoguild; ichnofacies.*

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The potential of ichnofossil data for cyclostratigraphic studies

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Ichnofabrics have been extensively utilized in paleoecological, paleoenvironmental, sedimentological, and stratigraphic analyses across all depositional settings. However, their application as indicators of cyclicity has been relatively underexplored. Most previous studies employed semiquantitative assessments of trace fossil density, type, and maximum burrow diameter to track Milankovitch cycles or to interpret climatic effects, such as *Zoophycos* cyclicity. This study uses ichnofabric data from the Ponta Grossa Formation (Paraná Basin) to investigate and quantify cyclic records. The analysis is based on core 2-TB-1-PR, as described by Plantz et al. (2024). Cyclicity was evaluated using three ichnofossil-based time series—bioturbation degree, ichnodisparity, and ichnofabric—derived from depth data. Gamma-ray logs used alongside sedimentary facies analysis to identify transgressive-regressive (T-R) cycles (Plantz, 2021) provided a control data series. Data preparation included linear interpolation for evenly spaced time series and detrending to remove low-frequency distortions. Power spectrum analysis was conducted using the multitaper method (MTM) with a smoothing window average to estimate background noise, while spectral changes were evaluated through MTM evolutionary analysis. All analyses were performed using the Acycle software package. MTM spectral and evolutionary analyses identified high-confidence components between frequencies of 0.008 and 0.026 cycles/m across all three-time series. Significant periods (at F-test significance level <0.05) were found as follows (in meters): 61.5 and 43.4 for ichnodisparity, 61.5 for bioturbation degree, and 46.1 for ichnofabrics. Gamma-ray time series analysis revealed periods of 65.5 and 44.5 m of thickness. The wavelengths of the ranked time series align closely with gamma-ray data, with minor differences attributed to data resolution. Filtering the selected frequencies revealed 9 cycles (Fig. 1) for all-time series. According to Plantz (2021), eight complete T-R cycles and one transgressive cycle, with thicknesses ranging from 40 to 80 m, are preserved in the core (Fig. 1). In conclusion, ichnofossils time series reflect cyclic behavior consistent with T-R cycles identified through gamma-ray logs and sedimentary facies analysis.

Keywords: paleoenvironment; applied ichnology; ichnofabric approach; Devonian.

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Fig. 1. Extracted filter with frequencies of 0.012177- 0.026608 cycles/m for bioturbation degree, 0.012627- 0.026157 cycles/m for ichnodisparsity, 0.0085687-0.025255 for ichnofabric, and 0.01122-0.02289 for gamma-ray.

Ichnofabric analysis from the Lower Cretaceous Río Mayer Formation (Austral Basin), Argentina

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The Río Mayer Formation is a unit accumulated in the Austral Basin (southernmost part of South America), during the Lower Cretaceous. This formation has been increasingly studied in recent years due to its importance as an unconventional reservoir. Although some previous publications cover the ichnology and sedimentology of this unit, herein we provide new data from the Estancia Cristina locality, where this formation comprises a 647 m-thick succession, being the most complete section recorded up to now, for this unit (Fig. 1A). An integrated sedimentological, ichnological, and petrological analysis was conducted at this locality, where four Facies Associations have been recognized. FA1 consists of organic-rich mudstones, completely bioturbated, with the development of a *Phycosiphon* ichnofabric, and with intercalations of calcarenitic and tuffaceous sandstones with an ichnofabric dominated by *Teichichnus*, and subordinately, *Cylindrichnus* (Fig. 1B). This facies association is interpreted as deposited in an upper to lower offshore. FA2 consists of completely bioturbated marlstones, with a more complex tiering structure, including levels with *Nereites*, *Phycosiphon*, *Planolites*, *Chondrites*, and *Zoophycos*. This facies association corresponds to an inner shelf deposit (Fig. 1C). FA3 consists of mudstones and heterolithic mudstones with isolated levels with *Nereites*, *Thalassinoides*, *Chondrites*, *Phycosiphon* and *Zoophycos*, showing a patchy distribution (Fig. 1D). FA3 is interpreted as formed in an inner shelf to upper offshore environment. FA4 comprises marlstones and laminated mudstones, with intercalations of very fine-grained sandstones, deposited in an upper offshore setting. This facies association lacks bioturbation, and shows the development of extensive levels of microbial mats (Fig. 1E). Characteristically, the Río Mayer Formation has been related to oxygen deficient conditions. However, our results point out that other parameters and processes were also critical for the establishment of the benthic fauna, among which organic matter input, episodic bottom currents, and upwelling should be considered to provide a supported paleoenvironmental reconstruction.

Keywords: Rio Mayer Formation; ichnofabric; Cretaceous; microbial mats.

Fig. 1. A. Schematic section of the Rio Mayer Formation in Estancia Cristina locality. B. Phycosiphon ichnofabric in Facies Association 1. C. Facies Association 2, with the typical tiering structure found in the marlstones. D. Isolated levels with trace fossils in deposits of Facies Association 3. E. Facies Association 4, lacking bioturbation and with development of microbial mats. Abbreviations: Ch: Chondrites, Ne: Nereites, Phy: Phycosiphon, Th: Thalassinoides, Z: Zoophycos.

Animal-substrate relationships in fluvial to coastal environments: Oligocene-Lower Miocene successions of the Colombian Caribbean

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This study examines key factors controlling animal-substrate interactions in progradational successions from fluvial to shallow-marine environments, focusing on ichnofabric characterization. It emphasizes dominant process regimes (fluvial-, wave-, or tide-dominated) while considering lateral facies variations. The research focuses on Oligocene-Lower Miocene sedimentary rocks from the Colombian Caribbean (San Jacinto Fold Belt, Lower Magdalena Valley Basin), associated to gas fields on the Caribbean margin.

The integration of sedimentological and ichnological information allows for the differentiation of several ichnofabrics that reveal paleoenvironmental changes in shoreface, wave- and fluvial-dominated deltas, intertidal zones, and patch reef settings.

Shoreface and wave-dominated deltaic deposits exhibit a higher abundance and diversity in the ichnofabrics, particularly *Ophiomorpha* and *Macaronichnus* ichnofabrics, indicating high-energy, low-turbidity conditions favouring coarse sediment deposition. Fluvial-dominated deltaic facies display reduced trace-fossil diversity, smaller trace sizes, and locally high bioturbation intensities, often linked to opportunistic colonization. *Phycosiphon* ichnofabric dominates under these conditions, but rapid environmental changes—such as cessation of torrential rains—promote transitions to *Ophiomorpha* ichnofabric, reflecting increased macrobenthic activity by mobile deposit feeders and surface-grazing organisms. Intertidal facies feature monospecific ichnoassemblages, i.e., *Thalassinoides* ichnofabric, with intermittent *Phycosiphon* ichnofabric occurrences likely linked to slack-water episodes requiring further assessment.

Patch reefs pose challenges due to localized facies heterogeneity, variable biotic community behaviours, and complex diagenetic overprints. However, *Thalassinoides* ichnofabrics associated with softground and firmground can improve paleoenvironmental assessments.

Ichnological research in coastal marine systems allow identification of predictable macrobenthic tracemaker responses to paleoenvironmental changes. However, these

preliminary patterns require further detailed studies. In this context, ichnofabrics approach along the same coastline and considering latitudinal variations in relation to paleogeographic context is crucial.

Keywords: *coastal marine systems; Colombia; ichnofabric approach.*

Paleosol ichnofabrics within a coastal alluvial parasequence from the early Miocene Kutch Basin, India

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Paleosol ichnofabrics in the lower Aquitanian Khari Nadi Formation of the Kutch Basin, India, have been characterized using a pedofabric/ichnofabric ternary diagram, with **OB**, **IF**, and **PF** as the end-member components (PITD; Fig. 1 for the acronyms). Five dominantly sandy paleosol suites including four ichnofabrics were recognized from the paleosol profiles P1–P4 (Fig. 1; Table 1). The *Taenidium*–*Rhizolith*–*Camborygma* ichnofabric from the basal paleosol profile (P1) evidences that with progressive pedogenesis, a pre-desiccation softground suite of *Taenidium serpentinum* and *T. barretti* developed, followed by the subaerial colonization of firmground *Camborygma litonomos* (and root traces) with a very shallow water table present (< 0.5 m). The *Beaconites*–*Camborygma*–*Rhizolith*–*Loloichnus* ichnofabric from the lower part of the overlying paleosol profile P2 (colonization surface P2₁) consists of *Beaconites antarcticus*, *Camborygma symplokonomos*, root traces, *Loloichnus baqueroensis*, and *C. litonomos*. These ichnospecies with increased burrow depth and intensified rhizoturbation signify a seasonally deeper and fluctuating water table. The upper part of the P2 paleosol profile (colonization surface P2₂) is characterized by a heterocomposite *Termitichnus*–*Camborygma*–*Loloichnus* ichnofabric, where *Termitichnus simplicidens* represents a substantial further lowering of the water table. The overprinting suite of *C. symplokonomos*, *C. litonomos*, and *L. baqueroensis* reflects the seasonal return of more moist soil condition. The overlying upper paleosol profile (P3) shows the development of a firmground *Thalassinoides suevicus* suite representing a short, likely autogenic, marine incursion and subsequent pedogenesis. The uppermost, thickest, and most well-developed paleosol profile (P4) comprises a well-developed *Rhizolith*–*Termitichnus* ichnofabric and conspicuous E- and B-horizonation. The rhizoliths' prominent tapering and branching upward morphology are interpreted as pneumatophore-associated structures, implying mangrove development. The roots and isopteran burrows make a crisscross boxwork pattern. As such, P4 may represent monsoon seasonality accompanied by a fluctuating water table and, soil horizonation, isopteran activity, and mangrove development. An unbioturbated transgressive biostromal carbonate lag deposit caps the P4 paleosol. The PITD plot and the ichnofabrics collectively define an early Miocene (proto-)monsoonal

condition with the following characteristics: (A) a shallow, seasonally fluctuating water table; (B) a stable and progressively shallowing-up condition with intermittent autogenic inundation; (C) OB being primarily overprinted by PF in the lower P2 and P3 and by IF in the P1, upper P2, and P4, and (D) mangrove development in the P4 paleosol.

Keywords: Early Miocene; paleosol ichnofabrics; Pedofabric/ichnofabric ternary diagram (PITD); *Termitichnus*; Mangrove.

Fig. 1. Pedofabric/Ichnofabric ternary diagram (PITD *sensu* Genise et al., 2004) of the studied paleosol profiles (P1–P4) from the Khari Nadi Formation. Abbreviations: OB- original primary sedimentary feature, IF- ichnofabric, PF- pedofabric. Here, in the case of P2₁ ichnofabric, PF (19%) and IF (32%) worked in tandem to destroy; In the P3 profile PF ((90%) was mostly responsible for the destruction of OB with a partial intervention of IF (10%).

Table 1: Percentage of each parameter of PITD diagram from four different paleosol ichnofabrics and one trace-fossil suite along with their ichnodiversity, OB, and PF components. * “Massive” is after Genise et al. (2004).

Paleosol profile	Paleosol ichnofabric	IF (%) range (avg.)	Ichnotaxonomic composition	OB (%) range (avg.)	OB components	PF (%) Range (avg.)	PF Components	Water table
P1	<i>Taenidium</i> – <i>Rhizolith</i> – <i>Camborygma</i>	30–50 (42)	<i>Taenidium serpentinum</i> and <i>Taenidium barretti</i> , <i>Camborygma litonomos</i> , and <i>rhizoliths</i>	50–70 (58)	Massive* sandstone	—	—	Shallow (<0.5)
P2	<i>Beaconites</i> – <i>Camborygma</i> – <i>Rhizolith</i> – <i>Loloichnus</i> (P2 ₁)	30–35 (32)	<i>Beaconites antarcticus</i> , <i>Camborygma symplokonomos</i> , <i>rhizoliths</i> , <i>Loloichnus baqueroensis</i> , and <i>C. litonomos</i>	25–60 (49)	Lenticular bedding	10–40 (19)	Platy peds	Deeper
	<i>Termitichnus</i> – <i>Camborygma</i> – <i>Loloichnus</i> (P2 ₂)	20–50 (31)	<i>Termitichnus simplicidens</i> cross-cut by <i>Camborygma symplokonomos</i> , <i>C. litonomos</i> , and <i>L. baqueroensis</i>	50–80 (69)	Massive* sandstone	—	—	Major deepening followed by shallowing
P3	<i>Thalassinoides</i> (suite)	5–15 (10)	<i>Thalassinoides suevicus</i>	—	—	85–95 (90)	Subangular blocky peds and associated cutans	—
P4	<i>Rhizolith</i> – <i>Termitichnus</i>	50	<i>Rhizoliths</i> (mangrove) and <i>Termitichnus simplicidens</i>	50	Massive* sandstone	—	—	Fluctuating water table

Ichnofabrics in Cambrian Burgess Shale-Type deposits: two case scenarios from Cranbrook and Stanley Glacier, Canadian Rocky Mountains

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Burgess Shale-type (BST) deposits are now beginning to be understood as formed in a diverse range of environments that share a similar, though yet not fully deciphered, type of preservation (e.g. Mángano et al., 2012, 2019; Saleh et al., 2022; Gaines et al., 2024). The dominance of minute, localized, and poorly penetrative trace fossils in these deposits has limited studies to simply use ichnofabric indexes or to attempt ichnotaxonomic determinations. Ichnofabric analysis in mud-rich depositional systems poses significant challenges (Wetzel and Uchman, 1998; Schieber, 2003; Paz et al., 2023). However, compared with other mud-rich deposits of younger age, BST sediments tend to offer relatively firmer substrates that preserve a variety of discernible morphologies and a wide range of sizes and depths of penetration.

Here, we focus on the diverse trace fossil modes of occurrence of two different localities, trying to explore them from an ichnofabric perspective. Cranbrook deposits have preservation of discrete structures, characterized by a strong size contrast and the localized presence of elite trace fossils formed by passively filled, centimetric-size burrows that obliquely cross the mud-dominated matrix interbedded with lenticular laminae of very fine-grained sandstone. Stanley Glacier deposits are characterized by irregular- and parallel-laminated fabrics, tiny to small, very shallow discrete structures. Still, bioturbated bedding surfaces and minor lamina disturbance in cross-section view reveal a complex story of fluctuations in environmental factors, such as oxygen and erosion and deposition rates, that allowed punctuated colonization events.

Previous characterization of BST ichnofabrics shows some similarities in patterns of bioturbation, typically exhibiting less than 5% biogenic disruption (BI= 1) with moderate bioturbation locally occurring (BI= 2–3). Most important, however, is to integrate ichnologic information with sedimentologic and stratigraphic data in ichnofabric analysis, defining micro-tiering and different types of ichnofabrics. This type of analysis allows us to reveal the interplay with physical processes and detect changes in diversity and ecologic interactions that can be illustrated in taphonomic pathways. Our results demonstrate how the application of ichnofabric analysis at lamina scale, combining both observations in vertical cross-section and the study of

exceptionally preserved trace fossils on sediment surfaces, is a powerful tool to reconstruct benthic life in BST deposits.

Keywords: *Burgess Shale-Type deposits; Cambrian; Cranbrook Lagerstätte; ichnofabric approach; Stanley Glacier.*

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A novel termite trace fossil from the early Miocene of Kutch Basin, India

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A new ichnogenus from Krausichnidae ichnofamily is described from sandy palaeosols of the Aquitanian Khari Nadi Formation from the Kutch Basin, India. The new material shows discrete chambers interconnected by a burrow system, documented on a vertical type area exposure of 30 m² (Fig. 1 A–B). The characteristic ichnotaxobases include the dominant vertical orientation of the burrows directly connected to the chambers (Fig. 1 A–F). These features distinguish them from ichnogenera, *viz.*, *Termitichnus* and *Vondrichnus*, where primarily the sub-horizontal and oblique burrows characteristically originate from the basal part of the predominantly equisized chambers. Although the new ichnogenus has similarities with *Parowanichnus*, the latter demonstrates consistently uniform burrow diameter and absence of lining surrounding the chamber. In this proposed ichnogenus, an individual chamber can be subspherical to oblate in shape (Fig. 1 C–E). The chamber diameter substantially fluctuates (i.e., 0.2–10 cm) reflecting the significant and characteristic morphological heterogeneity (Fig. 1 E–F). The chamber periphery exhibits varying degrees of preservation of the constructed wall and shows intermittent excavation. Chambers with varied fills (unfilled, passively filled, and actively filled) can be observed in the vertical section. The rare horizontal burrows sparsely connect at a right angle to the numerous shafts, thus, creating a distinctive reticulate pattern (Fig. 1 E–F). Both simple and compound (*i.e.*, a cluster of coalesced simple ones) shafts are common. Primary, secondary, and even tertiary branching can be documented. Root traces with their distinctive redoxiomorphic fabric are closely associated. The mutually cross-cutting relationship between the termite traces and rhizoliths suggests a mutualistic relationship rather than a sequence of successive colonization events. The characteristic vertical orientation points to a significant seasonal lowering of the water table that prompted deeper excavation for the optimum moisture required for nesting. Moreover, the dense bioturbation (BI 4) reflects the prolonged surface stability required for an extended colonization window. This preservation of the *Termitichnus* Ichnofacies represents a floodplain setting within a broader coastal alluvial depositional framework in a warm humid Aquitanian climate with seasonality (monsoonal?) and a closed-forest vegetation.

Keywords: Aquitanian; Krausichnidae; termite nest; *Termitichnus* ichnofacies, water table.

Fig. 1. A. Paleosol profile of Khari Nadi Formation, Kutch, Gujarat, from where new termite trace fossils are described (scale 20 cm), B. Schematic diagram of Fig. A, showing relict soil in the upper part (shaded in 'sand' colour); densely bioturbated pedogenized sandstone in the middle part (marked in light yellow) which contains newly described ichnogenera consisting of the chambers (marked in orange) and vertical galleries (marked in black); intensely bioturbated pedogenized and ferruginized sandstone (shaded in brown) in the lower part contains primarily root traces; C–D. Close outcrop photographs showing subspherical- to oblate-shaped chambers with differentially preserved constructed walls; E. closeup photograph of termite nests containing subspherical chambers and vertical galleries; F. Schematic diagram of Figure E showing a wide range of chamber sizes and burrow diameters (shaded in orange). Horizontal burrows rarely connect the vertical burrows creating a distinctive reticulate pattern. A mutual cross-cutting relationship with roots (shaded in yellow) has been shown.

Neoichnological expressions of salinity variability: Testing ichnological proxies in the Gironde Estuary and Arcachon Bay, France

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This study evaluates neoichnological characteristics of the Gironde Estuary and Arcachon Bay, France, to test ichnological proxies of salinity conditions along a freshwater to marine gradient. The Gironde Estuary is tide-dominated and Arcachon Bay is wave-dominated and tide-influenced (i.e., mixed-influence). Trace distributions and the size-diversity index (SDI) are determined at various localities in both systems and are then compared to trends established in prior studies. SDI is calculated by multiplying infaunal diversity (number of infaunal species) observed at each site (i.e., at all stations at each site) by the maximum measured *vermiform* burrow diameter. Vermiform animals include burrowing annelids, hemichordates and holothurians. The SDI captures changes in infaunal behaviour/trace diversity but also captures settings dominated by low diversity assemblages of large burrows wherein one species dominates to the exclusion of all others.

Results indicate that SDI provides a robust, quantitative correlation with salinity that is comparable to geochemical and biological proxies. Trace diversity alone reflects salinity qualitatively, but is limited by sampling and human (interpretation) bias and data variability. The findings contribute to a better understanding of the predictive value and limitations of SDI, refine ichnological approaches for estimating salinity, and demonstrate the application of ichnology in interpreting modern and ancient brackish-water systems.

Keywords: *salinity indicators; fluvio-tidal; neoichnology; size-diversity index.*

Reconstructing the history of a paleo-cliff: ichnologic insights of the Messinian-Pliocene unconformity in Bajo Segura Basin, SE Spain

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An integrated ichnologic analysis combining the ichnofacies and ichnofabric approaches was performed in the paleo-cliff and the shore platform recorded in the Messinian-Pliocene unconformity in the western Mediterranean (Bajo Segura Basin, SE Spain) (Soria et al., 2005; Caracuel et al., 2011). Various localities have been studied in the Colmenares area very close to Alicante with the aims of analyzing trace-fossil distribution in a paleo-rocky coast, deciphering its controlling factors, and evaluating the dynamics of the Pliocene flooding after the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC). First, two substrate-controlled ichnofacies have been recognized; *Glossifungites* and *Trypanites*. The *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies is recorded by *Thalassinoides* and *Rhizocorallium*. It occurs in notches and shore platforms carved in mudstone or marl due most likely to the rehydration of these sediments during flooding which have resulted in a firm substrate available for the benthic community. The *Trypanites* Ichnofacies is characterized by *Gastrochaenolites*, *Entobia*, *Caulostrepsis*, *Trypanites*, and *Meandropolydora*. The *Trypanites* Ichnofacies is preserved in micro-cliffs, notches, and shore platforms carved in limestone. Second, ichnofabric attributes such as bioturbation index, cross-cutting relationships, trace-fossil sizes, and tiering have been analyzed. *Gastrochaenolites* specimens are variable in both abundance and depth of penetration. For instance, in down-side surfaces of cliffs, within the notches, *Gastrochaenolites* is abundant and deep, whereas in the shore platforms specimens are truncated and less common. This pattern likely reflects longer colonization windows in the former, whereas shore platforms were continuously affected by wave erosion negatively impacting on the benthos (Fig. 1). In addition, a composite ichnofabric is locally recorded, consisting of a monospecific suite of erosionally truncated *Gastrochaenolites*, cross-cut by a higher ichnodiversity suite that does not show evidence of truncation. This ichnofabric reflects high-energy conditions on the shore platform, followed by low-energy conditions under deeper water, showing the evolution of the Pliocene flooding in the Colmenares area (Fig. 1).

Keywords: paleo-cliff; control factors; substrate-controlled ichnofacies; composite ichnofabric; Messinian-Pliocene.

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Fig. 1. Ichnologic features in a cliff, notch and shore platform system, and its evolution during flooding, Messinian-Pliocene unconformity in the Colmenares area (Bajo Segura Basin, Alicante, SE Spain).

Ichnofabric analysis and different time-scale palaeoclimatic variability: The Late Pleistocene Mid Brunhes Interval at the SW Iberian Margin

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The Mid Brunhes Interval (MBI) is a significant paleoclimatic period spanning 550-280 ka, characterized by a high amplitude of glacial/interglacial cyclicity, including Marine Isotope Stages (MIS) 14 to 7. Within this period, MIS 11 and 9 have been considered potential Holocene analogues due to extreme warming, high CO₂ concentrations, and elevated sea level; whereas MIS 12 and 10 represent the most important glacial phases of the late Pleistocene. Then, deposits corresponding to the interval between MIS 12 and 9 provide exceptional material for studying Pleistocene climate variability and its impact on macrobenthic trace maker communities.

Here we present an ichnofabric analysis of hemipelagic sediments deposited from MIS 12 to 9, within the MBI, at the International Ocean Discovery Program (IODP) Site U1385 in the SW Iberian Margin. The trace fossil assemblage consists of nine ichnogenera: *Chondrites*, *Ophiomorpha*, *Palaeophycus*, *Planolites*, *Scolicia*, *Taenidium*, *Teichichnus*, *Thalassinoides* and *Zoophycos*. Four ichnofabrics were defined: (1) *Thalassinoides* ichnofabric, (2) *Ophiomorpha*-like ichnofabric, (3) *Chondrites* ichnofabric, and (4) *Zoophycos* ichnofabric. Ichnofabrics distribution is closely linked to glacial/interglacial cycles. Interglacial intervals reveal stable and favourable conditions, favouring the development of *Thalassinoides* ichnofabric. In contrast, glacial periods, and especially Terminations, are characterized by less favourable conditions, promoting the presence of *Zoophycos* and/or *Chondrites* ichnofabrics. On a shorter time-scales (millennial scale), cold events do not show a strong control over macrobenthic tracemaker communities, but Heinrich type events are clearly associated to *Chondrites* ichnofabric in most of cases. A more detailed analysis, considering additional proxies related to surface primary production, bottom water ventilation and other palaeoenvironmental parameters, will provide further insights into the potential limiting factors for macrobenthic tracemaker communities, along glacial/interglacial variability and millennial scale events, and the feasibility of using ichnofabrics as proxies for such climatic phenomena.

Keywords: *IODP Site U1385; ichnofabric analysis; Mid Brunhes Interval; Marine Isotope Stages; Heinrich events.*

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***Glossifungites* Ichnofacies associated with stratigraphic discontinuities in Mesozoic–Cenozoic deposits of the Arauco Basin, Central Chile**

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The Arauco Basin (Central Chile) is situated within the coastal forearc domain of the Andean active margin of the South American Plate and forms part of a raised platform. It hosts a sedimentary succession approximately 2300 m thick, spanning from the Maastrichtian to the Holocene (Becerra et al., 2013). While the sedimentological characteristics of its stratigraphic units have been relatively well studied, the contact relationships between these units are insufficiently understood.

Within the Arauco Basin, five tectonostratigraphic sequences separated by unconformities have been identified (Becerra et al., 2013). From the base to the top, these sequences include: (S1) Late Cretaceous (Santonian–Maastrichtian), (S2) Paleocene–Middle Eocene, (S3) Lower Miocene, (S4) Pliocene–Pleistocene, and (S5) Pleistocene–Holocene. These correspond to the Quiriquina Formation, Lebu Group, Ranquil Formation, Tubul Formation, and Cañete Formation, respectively. Each of these sequences is bound by hiatuses spanning varying time intervals (Kuhn et al., 2010).

This study focuses on the trace fossils identified within four stratigraphic discontinuities across the Mesozoic–Cenozoic succession. The basal sedimentary sequence unconformably overlies Paleozoic metamorphic basement rocks, which have been reported to host *Gastrochaenolites* isp. (Buatois and Encinas, 2011).

Four major discontinuity surfaces were recognized, each with distinct ichnological characteristics:

SB1: Local colonization by *Gastrochaenolites ornatus* and *Rhizocorallium* isp.

SB2: Presence of *Gastrochaenolites*.

SB3: Sparse and localized occurrences of *Gastrochaenolites*.

SB4: Localized *Gastrochaenolites* with bimodal size distribution.

The trace fossils associated with these surfaces generally exhibit passive infill and vertical orientation. All of the surfaces assessed in this study were formed in coastal marine environments during significant sea-level falls, which led to exhumation and erosion, generating sequence boundaries. The surfaces were transformed into firmgrounds and

colonized during the early stages of transgression, leading to the development of the *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies.

Keywords: *Glossifungites ichnofacies; Gastrochaenolites; Rhizocorallium; Arauco peninsula; south-central Chile.*

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Ichnofabric insights into the impact of Late Devonian anoxic events on benthic ecosystems in North American

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During the Late Devonian, several anoxic events profoundly affected marine ecosystems, resulting in severe biotic crises, such as the Taghanic, Kellwasser, and Hangenberg events. These anoxic episodes are well-documented in the North American Seaway (NAS), a broad epeiric sea that covered much of North America. In the basins comprising the NAS, thick shale deposits accumulated during the Late Devonian, characterized by their dark color and the general absence of biogenic structures.

The present study aims to apply an ichnological approach, to these facies, focusing on ichnofabric characterization, to evaluate the impact of anoxic pulses on the macrobenthic tracemaker community inhabiting the NAS. The study sections include four cores from the NAS (poorly connected to the Rheic Ocean)—three from the Illinois Basin, one from the Appalachian Basin—and an additional core from the Anadarko Basin (directly connected to the open ocean). These cores are characterized by thick deposits of dark-grey to black shale units interbedded with thin layers of light-grey to greenish shales.

Ichnological analysis allowed to differentiate eight distinct ichnofabrics: i) unbioturbated/laminated ichnofabric, ii) mottled ichnofabric, iii) mottled and *Planolites* ichnofabric, iv) mottled and DOL ichnofabric, v) sandy-infill ichnofabric, vi) *Zoophycos* ichnofabric, vii) mottled and *Chondrites* ichnofabric, and viii) *Spreiten* ichnofabric. The distribution of these ichnofabrics in the study cores shows evident lateral and stratigraphic changes.

In the NAS, lower Frasnian intervals are characterized by alternating occurrences of the unbioturbated/laminated ichnofabric, dominant in dark facies, and ichnofabrics indicative of high ichnodiversity. Upwards, three to four anoxic pulses are marked by the recurrence of the unbioturbated/laminated ichnofabric, interrupted by oxic intervals evidenced by ichnofabrics featuring *Teichichnus*, *Planolites*, *Cylindrichnus*, *Chondrites* and mottled textures. Conversely, in the Anadarko Basin only the mottled ichnofabric was identified alternating with the unbioturbated/laminated ichnofabric in the lower Frasnian intervals, and then a persistent

scarcity of biogenic structures, with only mottled ichnofabrics is observed following the anoxic events.

Ichnofabric analysis reveals a significant variability, reflecting the differential effects of anoxic pulses across various depositional settings. Thus, the anoxic events impacting marine ecosystems during the Late Devonian were more pronounced in open-marine environments (i.e., Anadarko Basin) than in the epeiric basins of the NAS.

Keywords: *Black shales; epeiric seas; ichnofabrics; redox conditions; Late Devonian.*

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Preliminary report of a key surface of crowded-radial and *Rosselia* trace fossils in the Early Pliocene of the Bajo Segura Basin (Río Seco section, SE Spain)

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The Río Seco section, located in the southern sector of the Bajo Segura Basin (Alicante Province, SE Spain), was deposited in the first phases of the Pliocene flooding following the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC). At the beginning of the transgression, sedimentation took place mainly in the valleys and incisions formed during the sea-level fall connected with the MSC. Although ichnological analysis already allowed a detailed characterization of this first marine ingression (Caracuel et al., 2011), it was never applied to detect other key surfaces within the Pliocene deposits, once the marine sedimentation was well established. This is the case of the Río Seco section, where a singular trace fossil assemblage points out an interesting surface. The studied level is interbedded in an otherwise quiet, homogeneous section characterized by an alternance of sandy mudstones and fine-grained event beds most probably related to storms in a very shallow shelf environment. The bed is characterized by an extremely high abundance of deeply eroded *Rosselia* and radial trace fossils, herein preliminarily assigned to *?Haentzschelina*. A sandstone rich in *Macaronichnus segregatis* overlies this bed followed then by the normal muddy background sedimentation. The ichnological features of the *Rosselia* bed (e.g. deeply eroded *Rosselia*, very high density of the burrows, abundance of radial trace fossils) would appear to suggest a period of erosive episodes and low sedimentation rate, producing a sort of condensed interval clearly recognizable for its unusual ichnological content. The overlying *Macaronichnus* bed appears to point out a new pulse in the transgression, with the establishment of high-energy background currents for which *Macaronichnus* can be considered a proxy. In this context, the *Rosselia* bed would represent therefore a short-term, key condensed surface, marking most likely a sequence boundary within the Pliocene deposits. Further studies are planned in order to clear up the ichnotaxonomic position of the radial trace fossils, its relationship with *Rosselia* burrows, and to interpret the surface in the context of the Pliocene flooding after MSC.

Keywords: crowded radial trace fossil; key surface; *Rosselia*; Messinian-Pliocene.

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The *Gyrolithes*-*Thalassinoides* system to detect minor palaeoecological variations during the evolution of a river-influenced bay (Pliocene of the Bajo Segura Basin, SE Spain)

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Gyrolithes is a well-known helical trace fossil recorded in marine deposits since the Early Cambrian. Different hypothesis have been proposed to explain the particular geometry of these burrows, from those involving sediment exploitation for nutrition to those relating the geometry to buffering function against salinity changes. In this work, a Pliocene *Gyrolithes*-*Thalassinoides* complex system is studied, analyzing both the relative variation of *Gyrolithes* vs. *Thalassinoides* and its relationship to changes in the main ecological parameters. The Río Seco section, located in the southern sector of the Bajo Segura Basin (Alicante province, SE Spain), deposited in a shelf environment during the flooding after the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) in a context characterized by major palaeogeographic and palaeoenvironmental changes that importantly affected organisms. In this framework, sediments mainly accumulated in the incisions produced during the MSC sea-level fall. The study section is made up of interbedded sandy mudstones, where the *Gyrolithes*-*Thalassinoides* system develops, and laterally continuous fine-grained sandstones with very well preserved hummocky- and swaley-cross stratifications rich in *Ophiomorpha nodosa*. *Gyrolithes* is more abundant in the lower part of the section, while *Thalassinoides* is dominant in the uppermost one. In order to determine the variation of palaeoecological parameters as depth, salinity and organic matter input, a micropaleontological analysis was also carried out focused on the determination of benthic and planktic foraminifers, their relative abundance and the presence of ecological markers. The integrated study showed that i) the lower part of the section deposited in a confined bay with fresh-water influence and organic material coming from the continent, most probably related to the nearby mouth of the paleo-Segura River; ii) in this context, the great abundance of *Gyrolithes* could be related to the fresh water affecting the salinity of the bay, reinforcing the possible use of *Gyrolithes* as a proxy for low salinity anomalies iii) a slight shallowing-upward trend can be detected through sedimentological and paleontological features iv) toward the top of the section, *Gyrolithes* become rare respect to *Thalassinoides* as a result of a change in the physiography of the shoreline, with the formation of an opener bay, dilution of the river input and the consequent decrease of the impact of fresh-waters on the benthic community.

Keywords: *Gyrolithes*; river-influenced bay; salinity fluctuation; palaeoecological reconstruction; Messinian-Pliocene.

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Ichnofabric Index and Bioturbation Intensity: strengths, limitations, and the need for refinement

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This paper examines the history, utility, analysis, and nuances of quantifying (or semi-quantifying) bioturbation within an ichnofabric. Although seemingly straightforward, this process is often taken for granted, and estimates of the Ichnofabric Index (II)—one of the most commonly used frameworks—are rarely scrutinized or cross-checked against physically measured examples of similar bioturbation styles.

The Ichnofabric Index (II) provides a semi-quantitative approach by categorizing sedimentary disruption from II1 (unburrowed) to II6 (fully reworked). It evolved from Bioturbation Intensity (BI), which ranges from BI0 (unburrowed) to BI6 (biogenic homogenization) and places greater emphasis on preserved sedimentary fabric. While visual estimates of II and BI, often aided by comparators, are generally reproducible, they lack calibration against actual measurements and are sensitive to trace fossil assemblage size, type, and behavior.

A key issue with II and BI is their unequal binning structure. II1 represents a single fixed value (0% bioturbation), while II6 is effectively unbounded, exceeding 100% bioturbation in some cases. The other bins are of unequal values. This nonlinear distribution makes these indices unsuitable for statistical analysis. A linear framework may improve the semi-quantification of large ichnological datasets.

Another challenge with II and BI is interpreting II6 and BI6, as extreme bioturbation can lead to cryptic bioturbation—where pervasive and indistinct reworking obscures individual trace fossils and sedimentary laminae, creating a massive-appearing fabric. Interpreting such fabrics requires caution, as other processes like dewatering, rapid sedimentation, or a lack of grain contrast can also produce similar fabrics. To differentiate between these processes, key criteria include the presence of ichnofossils above or below the massive-appearing zone, burrowed bed contacts, or subtle grain reorientations (circular to elongate) in thin section.

The interpretation of II6 is highly context-dependent. These fabrics are often ascribed to slow sediment accumulation, such as on the outer shelf, but they can also form in high-energy, food-rich environments, like intertidal flats. An extreme case is *Macaronichnus*, where once-over deposit feeding in modern foreshore deposits can obliterate sedimentary structures within a single tidal cycle.

In summary, while assigning and interpreting II/BI may seem straightforward, it presents several challenges. On one hand, it provides reasonably repeatable datasets, capturing a key aspect of ichnofabric. On the other hand, statistical analysis of II/BI remains problematic and arguably inappropriate due to its inherent limitations. Additionally, interpreting II6 and BI6 is often more complex than assessing less bioturbated strata. As the need for statistical evaluation of large datasets grows, and advances in quantitative image analysis improve, new frameworks for assessing Bioturbation Intensity are likely to emerge.

Keywords: *Ichnofabric Index; Bioturbation Index; cryptic bioturbation.*

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On the beach. Behavioral traces from the intertidal zone of two Pacific beaches in Costa Rica

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The intertidal zone is a challenging environment for animals. Exposed to aerial, land and marine predators, as well as periods of wetting, desiccation, and varying degrees of wave energy, these animals have developed many behaviors that aid in their survival. Responses to the diurnal high and low tides on these beaches include burrowing to protect from desiccation at low tide and migrating with the tide to maintain a position relative to the wetted front on the beach. In this presentation, we discuss behaviors recorded on two Pacific beaches, Playa Grande and Playa Potrero, in Guanacaste province, Costa Rica.

The exuberance of life in the intertidal zone is evident in the simple, compound and complex traces resulting from animal activities. Most of these traces are evanescent, eliminated by the next set of waves, but some at the margins and subsurface may have a higher potential for preservation (Fig 1). Accompanying these traces are the remains of some of the tracemakers and other animals that live near the surf zone. The simplest class of traces are the tracks and burrow fields of single species such as *Olivella* foraging traces, hermit crab tracks and bird tracks. Some simple locomotion traces such as the *Trisulcus*-like trails of *Mellita sp.* culminate in shallow burrows. Examples abound of complex traces of burrows with their associated housekeeping or feeding traces, from the simplest such as the burrows of ghost crabs, to more elaborate radiating traces. Compound and complex traces of interactions include active hunting traces and predator avoidance traces, such as those of the gastropod, *Agaronia* hunting both *Donax* and *Olivella*, and the radiating patterns of multiple animals exploiting a central food source or foraging in a radial pattern from a burrow, as well as disturbed burrows.

The preservation potential of the surface traces may be low, but where they are found they can be used as environmental indicators, (e.g. the Cretaceous Woodbine Formation, East Texas, USA; Fig 1 right). The preservation of burrows and other subsurface traces may also be indicative of the intertidal environment, especially when seen in the context of accompanying traces, such as the pellet filled burrows of crabs, bird probing traces, and disturbed burrows indicating predation, the use of resources by multiple individuals, or escape activities.

Keywords: *intertidal; behavioral traces; Costa Rica; neoichnology; Cretaceous*

Fig. 1. *Left, Pelleted crab burrow orifice, Playa Potrero, C.R., January, 2025. Right, Fiddler Crab deposit, (“popcorn sand”), Woodbine Formation (Cretaceous, Cenomanian), Murrell Park, North Shore Grapevine Lake, Texas, USA. (ruler in inches).*

Superabundant *Chondrites* in offshore deposits of the Lower Devonian Le Faou Formation at Crozon Peninsula (France) and the role of outcrop exposure in assessing ichnofacies

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Ichnofacies are identified based on an evaluation of different ichnological and ecological parameters (e.g., ichnodiversity, trophic types, trace-fossil abundance) present across a specific stratigraphic interval. The quality of outcrop exposure can significantly alter ichnotaxonomic decisions made by an investigator and the record of specific ichnofacies because some ichnotaxa are better preserved on bed surfaces than in vertical cross-section, and *vice versa*. The identification of the *Cruziana* Ichnofacies, which is characterized by dominantly horizontal trace fossils and a high ichnodiversity, is favored by outcrops exposing common and large bedding planes, and is traditionally regarded as typical of offshore environments (below fair-weather wave base and above storm wave base). In this study, we present the case of offshore deposits from the Lower Devonian Le Faou Formation (Crozon Peninsula, Brittany, northwestern France) that are not characterized by typical constituents of the *Cruziana* Ichnofacies. The section investigated is 56 m thick and is composed of heterolithic mudstone and very fine- and fine-grained sandstone, the latter displaying abundant hummocky cross-stratification and symmetrical (wave) ripples. The peculiarity of the section is the subvertical orientation of strata (rotation/dip of 80°) that are frequently weathered by modern tides on the tidal flat and on the low-relief coastal cliff, hence providing excellent cross-sections of strata while bedding planes – and especially bed bases – are barely available (i.e., cliff and stepped cliff exposures of Shillito and Gougeon, 2023). Recorded ichnodiversity is very low and overwhelmingly dominated by *Chondrites*; bioturbation intensity in cross-section and on bed tops is null to fairly high (Bioturbation Index = 0–5, Bedding Plane Bioturbation Index = 1–5; see details on methodology in Gougeon *et al.*, 2025). The presence of abundant *Chondrites* burrows is typically regarded as characteristic of oxygen-deficient settings, and is a representative constituent of the *Zoophycos* Ichnofacies. Preliminary conclusions are twofold: that (1) the lack of bed base exposures significantly hampered the observation of trace fossils of the *Cruziana* Ichnofacies because bed bases are typically ideal to reveal shallow infaunal horizontal trails and burrows; and that (2) the pristine preservation of superabundant *Chondrites* in offshore transition, upper offshore, and lower offshore sub-environments seems to represent of genuine

ecological signal, and that their occurrence in a paucispecific ichnoassemblage suggests pore-water dysoxia in the substrate (Vossler and Pemberton, 1988). Further work is needed to evaluate the taphonomic pathway(s) that led to the formation and preservation of *Chondrites* and the origin of the food supplied to the sediment that seems to be significantly high.

Keywords: *ichnofacies; outcrop bias; Chondrites; Early Devonian.*

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Neoichnological insights from 3D photogrammetry: characterizing the microbial textures, sedimentary structures, and ichnology of the Bay of Fundy, Canada

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The Bay of Fundy is a well-studied, macrotidal estuary, renowned for having the largest tidal range on Earth. Three-dimensional photogrammetry with low-altitude unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) offers a unique opportunity to examine surface features in areas such as the Bay of Fundy, where logistical challenges, including tides, often hinder traditional detailed investigations.

This study focuses on three sites situated in the Bay of Fundy at different points along the estuary's salinity gradient: (1) the Salmon River in Truro, Nova Scotia; (2) the Petitcodiac River near Moncton, New Brunswick; and (3) Shepody, located north of Mary's Point, New Brunswick. These locations represent diverse estuarine environments and exhibit a range of surface textures and sedimentary structures.

The models capture fine-scale features, including microbially-induced sedimentary structures, such as elephant skin textures, alongside sedimentary structures formed by tidal and fluvial forces. In addition to these features, a variety of neoichnological trackways and trails are documented. These features are primarily produced by insect larvae and vertebrates such as shorebirds and raccoons.

The high-resolution orthomosaics and digital elevation models generated from UAV data allow for quantitative spatial analysis of lebensspuren distributions, revealing significant relationships between trackway characteristics—such as density, orientation, and morphology—and environmental factors including topography, tidal currents, and prey distribution. This research highlights the value of UAV photogrammetry in neoichnological studies, providing valuable insights into modern trace-making processes and their preservation potential. The resulting datasets not only enhance our understanding of contemporary tidal flat dynamics, but also offer important analogues for interpreting ancient tidal deposits and their associated ichnological signatures.

The lebensspuren, which primarily comprise horizontal tunnels, sparse vertical shafts, and various footprints, highlight the difficulties of employing the ichnofabric method in such low-

salinity brackish-water settings. The paucity of penetrative features and the potential preservation of tracks as indistinct deformational features are not well encompassed in ichnofabric methodologies, which are heavily cross-section-centric.

Keywords: *macrotidal; 3D model; photogrammetry; horizontal traces; neoichnology.*

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The giant Troll Field offshore Norway: treasury of gas, oil and ichnofabrics from a Jurassic deltaic ecosystem

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The Troll Field is the largest oil and gas field on the Norwegian Continental Shelf, with a production that accounts for about 11 percent of the EU's total natural gas consumption. An ichnological analysis of 42 cored wells from the Middle to Upper Jurassic (Callovian-Kimmeridgian) Sognefjord Formation of the Troll Field was performed to characterize the depositional system and to specify sedimentary environments. Key wells were logged in detail with respect to grain size, lithology, sedimentary structures, amount of bioturbation and trace fossils, which resulted in the calculation of ichnodiversity and ichnoabundance to infer sedimentary environments.

The studied successions comprise numerous metre-scale coarsening-upward sequences (parasequences) with muddy or silty fine sand in the lower part to medium or coarse sand at the top. In general, the amount of bioturbation is 100% in the lower and middle part of the parasequences and decreases to 0% towards the top. Ichnodiversity and ichnoabundance are also reduced upwards, although variations occur. The parasequences are systematically built by ichnofabrics, which are from the bottom to the top the *Phycosiphon*, *Teichichnus*, *Planolites*, *Ophiomorpha*, *Lingulichnus-Skolithos* and *Macaronichnus* ichnofabrics. Transitions and variations of these main ichnofabrics and combination with subordinate ichnofabrics indicate subtle changes in the environmental conditions and depositional processes. Most parasequences terminate at their top with a sharp boundary (e.g., flooding surface) and a break in facies, typically from relative shallow (proximal) to relative deep (distal) in the depositional system. The ichnofauna together with sedimentological characteristics indicates deposition in a wave-dominated to tidal-influenced delta system. The *Phycosiphon* and *Teichichnus* ichnofabrics result from relatively low-energy deposition in a prodelta to lower delta-front setting, which become replaced in a proximal direction by the *Planolites* and *Ophiomorpha* ichnofabrics (upper delta front and mouth bar) and non-bioturbated distributary channel deposits. The upper part of the parasequences and their top flooding surfaces contain the *Lingulichnus-Skolithos* ichnofabric. In the upper part of the Sognefjord Formation, the *Macaronichnus* ichnofabric occurs in interdistributary bays affected by storms, tides, freshwater and salinity fluctuations,

supporting an interpretation as bays on a lower delta plain that preserves lungfish burrows and tetrapod footprints.

Keywords: *Ichnofabric analysis; trace fossils; deltaic; Jurassic; Norway.*

Fig. 1. Trace fossils and ichnofabrics with importance from the Troll Field.

Marginal-marine and terrestrial ichnofabrics of storm-washover fans from the Georgia and South Carolina (USA)

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Storm-washover fans are sedimentary deposits that readily demonstrate how barrier islands in the eastern U.S. are migrating landward with sea-level rise. These deposits, which are typically caused by seasonal storms, are primarily composed of clastic sand but also may include coarser sediments. Fans are the result of storm surges that carry sediments from beach and offshore environments, with waves often breaching primary dunes and fans deposited on back-dune meadows, maritime forests, or salt marshes. Washover fans are ichnologically remarkable because they represent rapid changes in substrates that replace a previous suite of tracemakers and their traces with an entirely new and different suite. For example, sandy storm-washover fans deposited on top of salt marshes displace mud snails (*Ilyanassa obsoleta*), mud fiddler crabs (*Uca pugnax*), polychaetes, wading birds, alligators (*Alligator mississippiensis*), and other tracemakers of those environments. In the weeks following deposition, fans are colonized or otherwise altered by tracemakers, such as ghost crabs, sand fiddler crabs, hermit crabs, ants, solitary wasps, moles, shorebirds, and nesting sea turtles. These organisms also represent an ecologically mixed assemblage, with marginal-marine and terrestrial species affecting the same substrates. Given enough time, immediate colonization may transition to ecological succession, with new plant growth, fewer marginal-marine animals, and more terrestrial animals (e.g., insects, deer, raccoons). An ideal marsh-to-washover ichnofabric sequence would show salt-marsh traces of low-energy facies overlain by initially high-energy sandy deposits cross-cut by mixtures of traces made by marginal-marine and terrestrial animals and plants. For this study, we provide examples of modern ichnocoenoses from three Georgia (USA) barrier islands (Sapelo, St. Catherines, and Jekyll) and one South Carolina island (Edisto) and compare these to ichnofabrics in Pleistocene storm-washover deposits on St. Catherines Island (Georgia).

Keywords: *ichnofabric; neoichnology; Pleistocene; storms; washover fans; Georgia; South Carolina.*

***Arthropycus* ichnofabric? Preliminary data from the Tianguá Formation (Silurian, Parnaíba Basin) NE Brazil**

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Arthropycus Hall, 1852 is a common trace fossil in lower Paleozoic beds of the Parnaíba Basin of northeast Brazil. The most well-known record is of excellent 3-D preservations of *Arthropycus* in positive hyporelief, whereas the *Arthropycus* ichnofabric record receives less attention. This contribution describes a unique *Arthropycus* ichnofabric observed in the top of bedding planes of the Silurian (Llandovery) Tianguá Formation (Serra Grande Group, Parnaíba Basin) exposed at the Poti River Canyon in Piauí State, northeastern Brazil. The ichnofabric is characterized by horizontal burrows that branch from a main rectilinear burrow, forming clusters of straight to curved tunnels. The tunnels are ornamented by faint transverse ridges and the clusters form narrow or palmate fans. The burrow fill is similar to the host sediment, in places suggesting a discrete chevron pattern. It occurs in low-angle cross-stratified medium-grained sandstones, or in sandstones with wavy bedding (symmetrical ripples) deposited in tidal flats that might have been affected by delta discharge. Microbially-induced sedimentary structures (MISS), such as wrinkle structures and leveling ripples, occur in these bedding surfaces, which point to substrate biostabilization, which could have favored preservation of these burrows in plain view. *Arthropycus brongniartii* is the major component of this ichnofabric, with simpler, elongated tunnels attributed to *A. linearis* occurring subordinately. The burrows cover nearly the whole exposed surface, generating a dense network pattern (bedding-plane bioturbation index 5, in a scale from 0 to 6) that is locally overlapped by a *Psammichnites* ichnofabric. *Arthropycus* is a feeding burrow formed by deposit-feeding arthropods, likely trilobites. Thus, the presence of this dense, monotypical ichnofabric suggests an abundance of organic detritus inside the substrate, which served as a food supply for the tracemakers. The presence of MISS on the tops of these bedding planes allow to hypothesize that they could act as undermat miners. The findings presented here enable for a broader discussion of the *Arthropycus* ichnofabric significance for better understanding the dynamics of shallow marine and coastal settings during the early Paleozoic.

Keywords: *Arthophycus brongniartii*; *Silurian*; *biostabilization*; *Gondwana*.

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Ichnofabric analysis of the Porcupine Abyssal Plain during the last 60kyr

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During the annual "Porcupine Abyssal Plain Sustained Observatory (PAP-SO)" cruise in May 2022 aboard the RRS James Cook, three gravity cores were collected from different locations within the PAP-SO area (northeast Atlantic, 48° 50' N, 16° 30' W, at a water depth of 4850 m): (1) the flank of a small abyssal hill, (2) an abyssal plain surrounded by abyssal hills, and (3) an open abyssal plain far from any elevated topography. An ichnofabric analysis of these cores was conducted to study the response of the tracemaker community to paleoenvironmental changes over the past 60,000 years in this area. Particular focus was given to the environmental conditions during the deposition of ice-rafted debris linked to Heinrich Event 4 (HE4), which was clearly identified in previous studies. Despite the closeness of the three study sites—less than 20 km apart—significant ichnofabric differences were observed. The punctual occurrence of dense "Mycellia"/*Trichichnus* ichnofabrics in the abyssal plain surrounded by abyssal hills and in the open abyssal plain can be related to shifting paleoenvironmental conditions (i.e., bottom water oxygenation) in both areas. However, this ichnofabric is absent in the flank of the small abyssal hill suggesting constant bottom water oxygen levels. Moreover, the hill flank shows a low-density *Planolites* and *Thalassinoides* ichnofabric after HE4, while the abyssal plain surrounded by abyssal hills presents low and absent bioturbation in the pre- and post-HE4 interval, respectively. This study proves how habitat heterogeneity in abyssal settings affects tracemakers communities.

Keywords: *palaeoenvironment; deep sea; ichnofabric; Heinrich Event 4.*

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Tiering variations under different temperature regimes: Using experimental neoichnology to improve ichnofabric characterizations

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The vertical tiering of different types of burrows has been an important feature for ichnofabric characterization (Ekdale et al., 2012). However, the extent to which either burrow morphology or tiering relationships vary under different climate conditions is underconstrained. We conducted two sets of incubation experiments with common tracemakers from intertidal flats along the western shoreline of Long Island Sound, near Long Wharf Park, New Haven, CT, USA. The first set simulated a gradual increase from ambient seawater temperature of 20°C (+2°C per two days until reaching 30°C) while in the second set we implemented a 6-day marine heatwave (30°C). Burrow morphology was characterized at daily intervals throughout the duration of each set of experiments. In particular, we analyzed the tiering of: 1) *Polykladichnus*-analogous vertical to oblique lined burrows produced by polychaetes (*Alitta* undet. and *Nereis* undet.), with single or multiple Y-shaped upward-branching bifurcation and slightly horizontal burrows that maintain connection to the sediment-water interface.; and 2) *Chondrites*-analogous vertical and subvertical central burrows produced by polychaetes (*Drilonereis* undet. and *Lumbrineris* undet.) that branch at depth with dominant horizontal development forming a dendritic system; and 3) *Arenicolites*-analogous U-shaped burrows produced by amphipods (*Grandidierella japonica*, *Gammarus mucronatus*, *Microdeutopus* undet.).

We observed that, under gradual increases in temperature, the *Polykladichnus* tracemakers migrated upward, moving to a dominant upper-tier position. In contrast, we do not observe a similar tiering shift for this tracemaker under our heat-wave simulation. Under gradual increases in temperature (but not under heat-wave conditions) we observe a concurrent downward migration of *Chondrites* tracemakers, moving to a lower-tier position. However, in the case of *Arenicolites* tracemakers, under heat-wave conditions, the amphipods migrated downwards to a lower-tier position. These results highlight how different temperature dynamics may have disparate effects upon tracemakers. Extrapolation of these results to the fossil record may provide a critical window into infaunal ecological dynamics across past climatic perturbations and exemplifies that variations in the tiering of each specific trace fossil must be considered individually, depending on the hypothesized tracemaker.

Keywords: *neoichnology; experiments; ichnofabric; temperature dynamics.*

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***Chondrites* from the Hirnantian-Rhuddanian carbonates of Baltica**

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The Baltic region has a prolific carbonate succession deposited during the Ordovician and Silurian periods. Studies have been ongoing on these rocks to understand the environments and events of the early Paleozoic, and ichnology has emerged as a valuable proxy for this. A focus on the latest Ordovician (Hirnantian) to earliest Silurian (Rhuddanian) pinpoints the study to a significant event during which environmental changes culminated in the first of the “Big Five” mass extinctions. Trace fossils from this interval have been documented from a few locations, including Baltica, and the effects of the palaeoenvironmental conditions are observed to be reflected in the abundance, ethology, diversity, and disparity of the traces. However, in this study, the specimens of the trace fossil *Chondrites* are highlighted as indicators of some environmental changes, chiefly oxygenation conditions, based on their morphology and abundance.

Sampled from the Reinu Quarry in northern Estonia, *Chondrites* specimens from three lithostratigraphic units in the Hirnantian-Rhuddanian interval exhibit characteristics probably reflecting varying oxygenation levels during the trace-making process. *Chondrites* specimens from the Hirnantian Kamariku Member are depauperate, occurring in scarce patches on thin mud layers between thicker sandy limestone beds. Trace-making occurred in oxygenated conditions, which hindered the preservation of organics that support deposit feeding. In the overlying Koigi Member, a predominantly carbonate mudstone unit, *Chondrites* specimens show a variety of well-expressed morphologies that may indicate different species or morphotypes. These specimens are confined to bedding planes, though shafts connected to some of the specimens suggest conduits through which the trace makers moved to access layers containing food. Trace-making in this unit was under dysoxic conditions, where deposit feeding occurred due to the preservation of organic matter, though concentrated in thin layers. The lower part of the Varbola Formation, above the Koigi Member, is most likely of the Rhuddanian age and characterised by pervasive *Chondrites*, fluctuating in abundance in the alternating marly and bioclastic layers. Morphology is observed as circular to elliptical spots and short bars (sometimes with branches). Oxygenation levels remained low during this part of the Varbola

Formation deposition. However, the intermittent occurrence of bioclastic layers suggests oxygenation episodes.

Keywords: *Chondrites; palaeoenvironmental reconstructions; ichnology; Baltica; Paleozoic.*

Polychaete burrows from Barkley Canyon (Northeast Pacific, Western Canada): Reconstructing benthic response to internal wave-triggered sediment resuspension

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Submarine canyons have a unique morphology incising into continental margins often hosting enhanced benthic abundance and biodiversity relative to the open slope. Previous studies in Barkley Canyon in the NE Pacific off British Columbia, Canada, have shown a benthic community structure predominantly controlled by hypoxic conditions at the core of the oxygen minimum zone, seasonal nutrient input provided via upwelling and downwelling dynamics, and hydrodynamic energy from sea-surface storms, internal tides, and waves. While the epibenthic community in this region is relatively well known, studies focusing on bioturbation and biogenic structures have received comparatively less attention. Modern studies focusing on the benthos can provide information to reconstruct tiering in ancient communities. In Barkley Canyon, infaunal organisms, their diversity, and their contribution to the overall community structure are widely undocumented. *In-situ* time-series video data from Ocean Networks Canada's NEPTUNE observatory located at the canyon axis (985 m deep) allows the study of modern biogenic structures observed on the sediment surface to better understand the community composition and structure of pre- and post-disturbance events. During periods of low turbidity (June 25, 2018-March 27, 2019), a community dominated by burrowing polychaetes was observed in the video within the axis of the canyon. Sediment push-cores collected in June of 2024 by means of a remotely operated vehicle in that same location confirmed the presence of high densities of spionid polychaetes in the top 10 cm sediment layer. In contrast, during periods of relatively higher turbidity, these organisms and their structures were apparently absent. The local increase in energy in the canyon benthic boundary layer and high levels of particulate organic matter in the water column have been linked to internal waves that triggered the resuspension and transport of sediments up-canyon. Barkley Canyon hosts burrows with a density equivalent to a Bedding Plane Bioturbation Index of ~2. Due to the lack of available cross-sections, it is not possible to convincingly demonstrate if these burrows are simple or U-shaped. These domichnial structures are heavily mucus-lined, suggesting a high

preservation potential under appropriate conditions. Preservation of these burrows is dependent on hydrodynamic energy and sedimentation rate. Under rapid rates of sedimentation with comparatively low hydrodynamic energy and erosion, these structures could be preserved, resulting in the formation of ichnofabrics dominated by vertical burrows. Conversely, under high energy conditions and significant erosion, no evidence of these organisms would be preserved in the fossil record. The spionid burrows in the deposits studied represent a simple ichnofabric produced by one community reflecting a single colonization event in sediment accumulated along the canyon axis. From the perspective of the ichnofacies model, this example would represent an occurrence of the *Skolithos* Ichnofacies in a deep-sea submarine canyon. Interestingly, this example corresponds to an oxygen minimum zone, representing a departure from the typical well-oxygenated conditions that characterize this ichnofacies.

Keywords: *Submarine canyons; oxygen levels; ichnofabric; spionid polychaetes.*

Well-preserved large *Piscichnus waitemata* in marginal marine deposits of the Miocene Shirahama Formation, Japan

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An extremely well-preserved specimen of *Piscichnus waitemata*, a foraging or feeding trace of a fish or a mammal using a waterjet from its mouth, occurs in alternating beds of sandstone and mudstone of tidal flat deposits of the Miocene Shirahama Formation, SW Japan (Nara and Seike, 2017; Nara et al., 2020, in prep.). Although most *P. waitemata* were previously reported to be a mere dish-, bowl-, pot-, or plug-shaped structure, this specimen is associated with radially arranged small sediment lobes that are partially fringed the top margin of a plug-like structure whose height (depth) and maximum width are approximately 32 cm and 36 cm, respectively. Judging from modern ray's feeding structures, the radially arranged lobes are interpreted to be blown-out sediment redeposited during or immediately after the waterjet excavation by the tracemaker. Previously reported specimens would thus be truncated and partially preserved due to physical erosion or successive bioturbation. As the specimen occurs in a net depositional setting of a prograding tidal flat system, the blown-out sediment commonly obliterated before preserved in rock record would have successfully crossed the fossilization barrier. Given its relatively large size, the tracemaker was likely a ray, skate, or mammal. Moreover, considering the megafauna of the Northwest Pacific coast at that time, the possibility that the desmostylid was the tracemaker cannot be ruled out.

Keywords: *ichnology; palaeoecology; tracemaker; ray; Desmostylidae*

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An overview of the palaeoenvironment and palaeoecology of the forearc basins of the Early Miocene Southwest Japan Arc during rapid back-arc opening

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In the Early Miocene, more precisely, sometime between 18 and 16 Ma, the SW Japan arc was rapidly rotated clockwise up to approximately 41.7° due to the opening of a back-arc basin that is nowadays the Sea of Japan (Hoshi, 2018). The rate of the arc movement was extraordinarily rapid, reaching a few decimetres per year, far exceeding the rates of most modern plate motions. At the same time, another back-arc, now called the Shikoku Basin, which was lay to the south of the arc was spreading to form a young and hot oceanic plate. The SW Japan arc, moving southwards at high speed, was obducted onto the hot and therefore light oceanic plate. Forced subduction of the Shikoku Basin then began, causing rapid uplift of the inner forearc areas (Nara and Aikou, 2016; Nara et al., 2017). In addition, the subduction of the hot Shikoku Basin following these events led to pronounced volcanism in the forearc region (e.g., Kimura et al., 2005).

Such highly active tectonism undoubtedly influenced basin evolution and land profiles, and thus controls the local and regional sedimentation, both directly and indirectly affecting benthic ecosystems. This talk will review previous studies and present recent developments in the field. A summary is as follows:

Nara and Aikou (2016) is the pioneering study from this perspective: They proposed the “over-sedimentation hypothesis,” that “over-sedimentation,” i.e., very frequent and rapid sedimentation, induced by sediment mass production in the hinterland due to active tectonism, likely caused the colonisation of depauperate fauna and the dilution of their ichnofabrics throughout the Misaki Group, one of the Early Miocene forearc basin fills of the SW Japan Arc. Later, Nara (2019) conducted a comparative study between the Misaki and almost coeval Tanabe basins and found that the uplift of the hinterland of the Misaki Basin was not only influenced by the forced subduction of the hot oceanic plate alone, but also by the magma ascent due to the accompanying and subsequent volcanism.

Meanwhile, reflecting the extremely active tectonism, shallow marine to marginal marine deposits in the forearc basins yield many seismic, tsunami-induced, or mass movement

deposits. The present author's groups have already reported some examples of such deposits (Nara et al., 2017, submitted; Imai and Nara, 2022), but many others remain unreported.

Although Nara and Aikou (2016) highlighted lack or considerable paucity of ichnofabrics and less diverse ichnocoenoses of the Misaki Group, detailed observations of such ichnofabrics and ichnocoenoses would lead to new horizons in our knowledge of environmentally stressed ichnological signatures. Moreover, as various types of tsunami deposits, including some mega-tsunami deposits (cf., Nara et al., in prep.), have been found to date, it would be interesting to construct comprehensive tsunami deposit facies model, or to evaluate the effects of tsunami deposition on benthic communities.

Keywords: *sedimentology; ichnology; ichnofabric approach; palaeoecology; palaeoenvironment.*

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Ichnofabrics formed by dense polychaete populations in lagoons: (paleo)ecological and preservational insights

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Polychaetes are well-known marine burrowers throughout the Phanerozoic, producing a variety of burrow architectures, ranging from simple vertical shafts to intricate multi-directional galleries. Polychaetes are also noted for living in dense numbers, resulting in crowded ichnofabrics. In this contribution, we describe the occurrence of dense polychaete burrows from the bottom of the Peixe Lagoon (southernmost Brazil) and discuss (i) the value of their crowded ichnofabrics as a bioindicator of tolerance to environmental stress and (ii) potential variations in their preservation in the fossil record, as well as the implications for conservation paleobiology.

The burrowing benthic fauna is dominated by polychaetes and bivalve mollusks, with the nereid polychaete *Laeonereis acuta* (Treadwell, 1923) accounting for almost 90% of the individuals. Salinity ranges from 9.6 to 12.5 ppm (winter/spring) and 23.6 to 24.5 ppm (summer/fall), and it influences *L. acuta* populations, which are denser in the summer (510 burrows/m²). Microbial mats cover practically the whole lagoon bottom and concentrate a large amount of organic material below a thin cap (≤ 5 mm) of an oxic cyanobacteria-dominated biomat. *L. acuta* digs vertical shafts or long and arcuate Y-shaped burrows with 3-5 mm in diameter, coated by a thin (≤ 1 mm), rust mucus lining. The burrows generally occur close together, but they do not intersect. *L. acuta* is a stress-tolerant organism that can withstand salt and water level variations, as well as oxygen depletion in the substrate, and can tolerate bottom exposure while the microbial mats keep the substrate moist for several days. Thus, their burrows will be the primary component in the ichnofabric generated by population succession over time, in a pattern similar to a low-diverse *Skolithos* ichnocoenosis composed chiefly by *Skolithos*- and *Arenicolites*-like burrows. Biofilms/microbial mats and the mucus lining play a significant role in burrow stabilization, ensuring a high potential for their preservation in the fossil record as either a crowded ichnofabric or a piperock.

Skolithos piperocks are common in Lower Paleozoic strata and they are typically regarded as opportunistic colonization of barren substrate in shallow marine environments. The data provided here suggest that this ichnofabric could possibly reflect also coastal,

lagoon/estuarine environments with successive colonization by stress-tolerant organisms rather than opportunistic ones.

Keywords: *vertical burrows; stress-tolerance behaviour; estuarine bioindicator; neoichnology.*

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Bioerosional traces in a foraminiferal test

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Even though foraminifera are a major element in all modern marine communities, sometimes comprising 50% or more of the eukaryotic biomass (Gooday et al., 1992), their trophic level is poorly investigated and in general not fully understood. Their full life cycles are only known for a handful of modern species despite a growing interest from the scientific community. Modern foraminifera seem to inhabit all marine environments and display a large variety of feeding modes, which include both parasitic and predatory behavior. The latter appears to be common in the benthic as well as planktonic realms. This and previous studies have shown that bioerosional traces on foraminiferal tests are quite common in many modern and fossil environments (Walker et al., 2017). A few of the tracemakers are known, but most are not. Likewise, it is also unknown why such organisms make these traces. A recent study of modern benthic foraminifera seems to suggest that a connection between the level of pollution and the number of borings in the foraminiferal test exists.

Some species of foraminifera are known to excavate pits or borings in different substrates such as the tests of dead as well as living organisms or limestone rock (Vénec-Peyré, 1996). A few species of benthic foraminifera demonstrate what seems to be a parasitic or predatory mode of life. However, many more species are believed to have a similar behavior due to their ability to bore into different substrates and tests of calcareous organisms, including other foraminifera.

Keywords: *foraminifera; paleoenvironment; trophic level; borings; predation; parasites.*

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Ichnofabrics at the Pliocene–Quaternary boundary, GSSP section in Sicily: standard or puzzling?

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The Global boundary Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) defining the Quaternary System, Pleistocene Series, Lower Pleistocene Subseries, and Gelasian Stage (Gibbard and Head, 2009, 2010; Gibbard et al., 2010; Head et al., 2020) is exceptionally exposed in the Mediterranean badlands (Italian “calanche”) at Monte San Nicola, approximately 10 km NNW of Gela, Sicily. The GSSP, dated to 2.58 Ma, is located at the base of a marly layer immediately above the Nicola bed. This bed marks the uppermost of six precession-related darker beds (A1, A2, A3, A4, A4/5, and A5) reflecting precession minima amplified by increased eccentricity (e.g. Capraro et al., 2022). Trace fossil analysis of the GSSP section at Monte San Nicola conducted in the spring of 2024 provides insights into fluctuating dissolved oxygen levels in pore and bottom waters during deposition, revealing the dynamic relationship between climate variability and seafloor ventilation (Monedero-Contreras et al., 2023). This study presents for the first time a high-resolution ichnological record of the Pliocene–Pleistocene transition, spanning approximately 10 m from 2.72 to 2.58 Ma and including the GSSP. Additional analysis of the sapropelic Nicola bed, approximately 20 cm thick and deposited over ~3000 years, shows a progressive shift from anoxic to oxic conditions just before the end of the Pliocene. The ichnoassemblage includes *Chondrites*, *Trichichnus*, *Planolites*, *Halimedides*, and *Phymatoderma?* (Fig. 1) which was previously interpreted as *Thalassinoides?* on the basis of vertical sections (Radmacher et al., 2023, 2025). Its assignation to *Phymatoderma?* is now possible due to several sections along the burrow, which reveal low-angle branching and only locally preserved densely packed, variably oriented pellets. Poor preservation of pellets is related to the presence of expanding clay minerals. The top of the Nicola bed is bioturbated over an interval of at least 5 cm, obscuring the precise location of the GSSP. Sedimentological and ichnofabric analysis, determined from vertical polished sections, supported by X-ray computed tomography (CT), reveals the distribution of *Trichichnus*, which is present above but largely absent from the Nicola bed. The lowest occurrence of *Trichichnus* just below the top of the Nicola bed may therefore serve as a practical marker for the Pliocene–Quaternary boundary.

X-ray CT proves an effective non-destructive method for detecting *Trichichnus*, which is often not visible on polished surfaces (Radmacher et al., 2023, 2025).

This study is part of the GELSTRAT program, an international collaborative initiative that incorporates a variety of approaches, including study of calcareous nannofossils, foraminifers, pollen, dinoflagellate cysts, macrofossils, ichnofossils, foraminiferal stable isotopes, organic geochemistry, clay mineralogy, magnetostratigraphy, ITRAX, and ¹⁰Be analysis. A more refined characterization of the Gelasian GSSP aims to improve its application for accurately identifying the base of the Quaternary on a global scale.

Keywords: *Gelasian GSSP; Plio-Pleistocene; trace fossils; X-ray 3D computed tomography.*

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Fig. 1. Ichnofabrics at the Pliocene–Pleistocene boundary, Monte San Nicola, Sicily, southern Italy. A) Vertical polished section of the rock block spanning the sapropelic Nicola bed. B) X-ray 3D computed tomography scan of the same block, with red lines indicating the *Trichichnus* structures. The thickness of the Nicola bed is 19.6 cm. C) Polished surface from the interval above of the Nicola bed, showing various trace fossils: 1) weakly visible *Trichichnus* isp., 2) larger burrows infilled with fossilized foraminifera (left), and with brighter material (right), 3) *Chondrites* isp. D) Polished surface showing subcylindrical, horizontal to slightly oblique structures identified as *Phymatoderma?* isp. E) Region of *Phymatoderma?* infilled with densely packed, variably oriented pellets.

Ichnofabric analysis of the Upper Ammonitico Rosso in the External Betic Cordillera (Cañada del Hornillo section Subbetic, Spain)

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This study analyses a lower Bathonian to Kimmeridgian (Jurassic) sequence of the Upper Ammonitico Rosso Formation, outcropping in the External Betic Cordillera (Subbetic, Cañada del Hornillo section, Córdoba province), focusing on the lithofacies characterization and the presence of trace fossils. The succession consists of red to white marly to calcareous, pseudonodular to nodular deposits. Within the succession, a hardground and a gap affecting upper Bathonian and Callovian, occur. The results are based on facies analysis from field observation and microfacies, with a description of textures and trace fossils observed in thin sections and polished slabs.

Four main types of lithofacies were differentiated according to macroscopic features:

- (1) Massive limestones: these constitute the base of the succession and they are characterized by the presence of an abundant ammonoids and the trace fossils *Arenicolites* and secondarily *Thalassinoides*.
- (2) White pseudonodular limestones: beds with pseudonodular appearance, densely bioturbated with *Thalassinoides*, rich in ammonite moulds and gastropods. Laterally there are brecciated levels where pebbles are affected by the boring *Gastrochaenolites*.
- (3) Nodular marly limestones: these strata have a distinct nodular appearance, with white nodules embedded in a red marly matrix, locally with abundant *Thalassinoides* that disappear when nodularity increases.
- (4) Hardground: this level marks the top of the Middle Jurassic succession and it is characterized by a surface enriched with *Thalassinoides* and Fe-Mn oxyhydroxide encrustations in a reddish matrix.

The infilling of *Thalassinoides* from the white pseudonodular limestones and nodular limestones appears laminated. Under microscope, the lamination is due to dense packing of oriented thin-shelled bivalve fragments (filaments), that ranges from wackestone to packstone. The filling of *Thalassinoides* from the hardground surface exhibits a sandy granulometry and ferruginized walls.

The facies variations observed in the Cañada del Hornillo section reflect complex interactions among sedimentation rate changes, bioturbation, and submarine winnowing. These processes, followed by early marine dissolution and diagenesis, significantly influence the alternation between pseudonodular and nodular textures in the Rosso Ammonitico facies.

Keywords: *trace fossils; microfacies; palaeoenvironment; Middle Jurassic.*

Trace fossil assemblages from the lower Toarcian Marrat Formation (Saudi Arabia)

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The early Toarcian global change, known as the Jenkyns Event and the Toarcian Oceanic Anoxic Event, has been commonly related to organic-rich facies in the Tethyan region and at global scale, and characterized by a negative carbon isotopic excursion (CIE). In Arabian Plate, this event has been recorded in the reddish siliciclastic unit of the Marrat Formation (Alnazghah et al., 2022), mainly constituted claystones, siltstones and sandstones. These red beds have been interpreted as shallow marine deposits and show the characteristic negative CIE of the Jenkyns Event (early Toarcian). The Middle Marrat red beds are limited by platform carbonates of the Lower Marrat and the Upper Marrat. Ammonite record indicates the upper *Tenuicostatum* and *Serpentinum* zones (lower Toarcian) for the Lower Marrat and the Bifrons Zone for the Upper Marrat (middle Toarcian) (e.g., Enay et al., 2021). Three main facies associations have been differentiated in the Middle Marrat representing distinct environments: (1) mixed wave and river-dominated delta front to prodelta, (2) tidally-influenced distributary channel, and (3) shoreface strandplain and underlying shelf.

Claystones and siltstones are not bioturbated. Trace fossils are commonly related to reddish, very fine to fine-grained sorted sandstones with *Arenicolites*, *Rhizocorallium*, *Lockeia*, and *Petroxestes*, locally with hummocky-cross stratification with *Skolithos* and *Cylindrichnus*. Some surfaces present dense *Rhizocorallium* and dense *Cylindrichnus*. Moreover, some pavements of small-size bivalves and microgastropods (< 2 mm long) are recorded. The sedimentary succession is organized in coarsening upwards sequences from reddish claystones and siltstones (offshore/prodelta) to reddish sandstones (shoreface strandplain to wave-river dominated delta).

The transition to Upper Marrat platform limestones (Bifrons Zone) is marked by the record of bioclastic calcarenites rich in bivalves, *Rhizocorallium*, *Thalassinoides* (from 2 to 9 cm thick), and *Planolites*. Locally there is a dense packstone of disarticulated thin-shelled bivalves (< 1 cm). The rest of the Upper Marrat is constituted by pseudonodular limestones (wackestone with

bivalves, gastropods and agglutinated foraminifera) locally with dense bioturbation by *Thalassinoides*.

Sedimentological and ichnological data point to the existence of asymmetrical wave-dominated shorelines with evidence of river flows and tidal processes during the deposition of the Middle Marrat red beds. The transition to the shallow carbonate platform of the Upper Marrat is characterized by the opportunist colonization by small bivalves that mark the flooding of the Arabian Plate.

Keywords: *Palaeoenvironment; sea-level changes; Jenkyns Event; Toarcian.*

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Ichnology and bottom dynamics of a carbonate dominated Miocene canyon (Eastern Mediterranean)

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Extensive canyons carved into the margins of the Levant Basin during the Oligocene–Miocene provide valuable case studies for understanding canyon fills in carbonate settings. While many studies have addressed their sedimentological features and processes at seismic and outcrop scales, detailed insights into the seafloor conditions in these canyons before, during, and after the occurrence of down-canyon processes that remobilize the sediment in the canyon remain limited. Ichnological studies may improve the knowledge on the paleoenvironmental conditions at the seafloor within these canyons. This study investigates the carbonate Pattish Formation along the margins of the pre-evaporitic Messinian Beer Sheva Canyon in Israel using an ichnofabric approach to characterize the evolution of seafloor conditions during different stages of canyon development. Three phases of canyon development are identified: 1) slope incision and headward erosion initiated by tectonic uplift and eustatic sea-level fall during the Early Oligocene, this phase was dominated by bioerosion and later large slope failures in the latest Middle Miocene, characterized by completely bioturbated sediments without discrete trace fossils; 2) platform incision and connection with a fluvial system in the Late Miocene related to falling sea level and tectonic uplift, and 3) canyon infill initially dominated by pelagic marl deposition in the canyon center, this phase transitioned to calcarenite clinobeds at the flanks, formed by gravity flows. These deposits display a proximal-to-distal ichnofabric zonation with varying ichnoassemblages and bioturbation indices. Finally, carbonate production along the canyon margins led to reef development and associated slope progradation toward the canyon axis. This stage is marked by a decrease in bioturbation intensity accompanied by an increase in burrow size.

Keywords: *palaeoenvironment; applied ichnology; ichnofabric approach; Messinian.*

Geochemical compositional mapping of restricted-basin to carbonate-slope deposits (Neogene, Maldives)

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The Maldives Archipelago provides a unique record of carbonate platform evolution and palaeoenvironmental conditions influenced by orbitally induced sea-level fluctuations and oceanographic changes during the Oligocene to Miocene. Integrating geochemical compositional mapping, ichnofabric analysis, and seismic data, this study characterizes slope and restricted basin deposits recovered during IODP Expedition 359 (2015), emphasizing their ichnological and geochemical attributes as proxies for palaeoenvironmental reconstructions. The Oligocene organic-rich (up to 30% organic carbon) sapropelic intervals exhibit low bioturbation indices and trace-element profiles consistent with oxygen-depleted bottom waters, while organic-poor sediments show high bioturbation indices and reduced organic carbon content (< 0.1%). Elemental mapping of trace fossils, such as *Thalassinoides* (*Th*), *Planolites* (*Pl*), *Zoophycos* (*Zo*), *Chondrites* (*Ch*), and *Phycosiphon* (*Ph*), reveal distinct geochemical signatures within burrow fills, which differ from surrounding sediments. These signatures, including Ca and S depletion in large burrows (*Th*, *Pl*), in Fe and S enrichment in others (*Zo*), and Fe, P, and S enrichment in the smallest *Chondrites* and *Phycosiphon* galleries. Such geochemical contrasts reflect sedimentary redox gradients and underscore the potential of burrow fills to preserve palaeo-oxygenation signals even when bulk sediments are homogenized. The overlying platform slope deposits reveal transitions from poorly oxygenated conditions during the Oligocene to improved ventilation following the opening of eastern platform passages (~17.5 Ma). Variations in ichnofabric diversity and bioturbation intensity correspond to changes in platform shedding, sea-level oscillations, and basin oxygenation, likely related to orbital cyclicity. This multidisciplinary approach demonstrates that ichnofabric analysis, combined with geochemical compositional mapping, provides critical insights into the sedimentary dynamics and palaeoenvironmental evolution of carbonate platforms. By linking ichnological and geochemical data, this study enhances the understanding of orbital and high-frequency controls on sedimentation and seafloor conditions, offering a model applicable to analogous depositional systems worldwide.

Keywords: *palaeoenvironment; applied ichnology; ichnofabric approach; geochemistry; Oligocene-Miocene.*

Paleoproterozoic eukaryotes

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The origin of eukaryotes, our own domain of life with nucleated cells, has been traced back to latest Paleoproterozoic marine acritarchs, dated at 1.7 Ga (Cohen and Kodner, 2022), but there are indications from terrestrial trace and body fossils for much greater geological age. The oldest eukaryotes are not to be found among microfossils, but among trace fossils, of the 2.3 Ga Medicine Peak Quartzite of Wyoming, first described as animal burrows by Kauffman and Steidtmann (1981). They are not animal burrows, but were redescribed as traces of rope-forming cyanobacteria (*Erythronema ramosum*) and as fungal vesicles of probable eukaryotic fungus (glomeromycotan) affinities (*Koilosolos pravus*) from Gypsid paleosols of the slightly younger 2.2 Ga Sugarloaf Quartzite in the same general locality (Retallack, 2020). The ferruginized cyanobacterial ropes are like fossil root traces, but the fungal vesicles are body fossils. Newly collected specimens of these species from the 2.3 Ga Medicine Peak Quartzite are illustrated here (Fig. 1E-F).

Other fungal vesicles are *Diskagma buttoni* from the 2.2 Ga Waterval Onder Vertisol paleosol in the Dwaal Heuvel Formation at Waterval Onder, South Africa (Fig. 1C-D). *Diskagma* is most like the endocyanotic glomeromycotan *Geosiphon pyriformis*, a modern fungus of forest soils which encapsulates nostocalean cyanobacterial symbionts within a large vesicle (Retallack et al., 2013). Although *Geosiphon* is a symbiosis of eukaryotic fungus and prokaryotic photobiont, not all lichenologists accept it as a lichen.

Living slime molds (Amoebozoa, Dictyostelida) are eukaryotic organisms living like amoebae dispersed in the soil until nutrient shortages stimulate them to aggregate into a slug (grex) capable of moving decimeters to new sites to sporulate and disperse. The grex leaves a clear trail with lateral levees, and marks similar to spreiten that are convex in the direction of travel, rather than in the opposite direction for worm trails. The trail flares in the direction of travel as isolated amoebae join the moving and swelling grex, unlike worm trails of constant diameter. Trace fossils of this sort have been indentified as *Myxomitodes stirlingsensis* from Fluvent paleosols of the 1.9 Ga Stirling Quartzite of Barnett Peak, Western Australia (Retallack and Mao, 2019).

Steranes of eukaryotes require oxygen for their formation (Cohen and Kodner, 2022), so the origin of eukaryotes may have required the Great Oxidation Event of 2.4 Ga, and originated on land, rather than at sea.

Keywords: *fungus; vesicle, slime mold; grex; paleosol; trail.*

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Fig. 1: Paleoproterozoic trace and body fossils: A-B, *Myxomitodes stirlingensis*, slime mold trail from the 1.9 Ma, Stirling Quartzite of Western Australia (Retallack and Mao, 2019); C-D, reconstruction and paleosol of *Diskagma buttoni*, *Geosiphon*-like endosymbiotic fungus from the 2.1 Ga Dwaal Heuvel Formation of South Africa (Retallack et al., 2013); E-F, *Koilosolos pravus*, fungal vesicles, and *Erythronema ramosum*, rope-forming cyanobacteria, from the 2.3 Ga Medicine Peak Quartzite at Lookout Lake, Wyoming (specimens collected in 2022, in Condon Collection, University of Oregon, F129631 and F129633 respectively).

The *Curvolithus* ichnofacies reconsidered

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The *Curvolithus* ichnofacies accommodates trace-fossil assemblages dominated by shallow, wandering horizontal burrows and internal trails such as *Arthropycus brongniartii*, *Curvolithus*, *Gyrochorte*, *Macaronichnus*, *Neoeione*, and *Olivellites*, usually accompanied by minor components of other morphologies. Most of these are combined feeding-locomotion burrows, though *Curvolithus* itself is probably a locomotion structure made by predators.

In 1984, Heinberg and Birkelund described a *Curvolithus* ichnocoenose in the Jurassic Vardekløft Formation of East Greenland and noted analogous modern trace associations. Seeing a similar assemblage in the Pennsylvanian Minturn Formation of Colorado (USA), Lockley et al. (1987) erected the *Curvolithus* ichnofacies, giving several additional examples from the literature. These were not considered to be sufficiently widespread in time or space by later workers such as Buatois et al. (1998) and MacEachern et al. (2012), and accordingly the ichnofacies received little attention by subsequent workers.

However, representatives now can be cited from the Silurian to Holocene in strata generally assigned to the *Cruziana* ichnofacies. Examples generally occur in sandy strata deposited on the continental shelf with water energy intermediate between the *Skolithos* and typical *Cruziana* ichnofacies. Bioturbation is generally incomplete and the traces may be accompanied by bidirectional ripplemarks. Wave energy is evidently sufficient to rework and maintain a sandy seafloor as such, making it difficult to maintain stable burrows and continually erasing the activity of tracemakers until the beds are buried.

It should be understood that identification of the *Curvolithus* ichnofacies does not require the presence of the name-bearing ichnogenus *Curvolithus*, just as recognition of the *Cruziana* ichnofacies does not depend on the presence of *Cruziana*, despite some confusion over this in the past. Sparse occurrences of *Curvolithus* within a diverse assemblage are not representative of the *Curvolithus* ichnofacies, but a dense occurrence of *Olivellites* in a depauperate assemblage may be.

And indeed, some have questioned whether the ichnofacies concept itself is now outmoded. McIlroy (2004) pointed out that an ichnologist should bring *all* available evidence to bear on interpretations of ichnostratigraphy and paleoecology. To this, I can only agree: I hope to bring another tool to bear within the framework of our research.

Keywords: *Curvolithus ichnofacies*; *ethology*; *fodinichnia*; *repichnia*.

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Ichnofabric analysis of ODP Site 1240: deep-sea water conditions at the Eastern Equatorial Pacific during the Mid-Pleistocene Transition

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The Eastern Equatorial Pacific (EEP) is a key area for understanding atmosphere/ocean dynamics and past climate fluctuations. This area has been profusely studied from several points of view including sedimentological, micropaleontological, and geochemical/isotopic analyses, among others. Particularly, of special interest is sediment core ODP Site 1240, recovered from a small trough at the Panama Basin in the EEP, north of the Carnegie Ridge and eastward of the Galapagos Islands. Previous studies revealed changes in paleoenvironmental conditions, such as oxygenation, organic matter, and sea surface temperatures, during the Quaternary associated to variations in the atmosphere-ocean system affecting biogeochemical features. Of special interest, the Mid-Pleistocene Transition (MPT), involving a major event in the Earth climate; dominant periodicity of climate change progressively from low-amplitude 41-ka obliquity-forced climate cycles of the earlier Pleistocene to high-amplitude 100-ka cycles in the later Pleistocene, without any significant change in orbital forcing. Here we present a preliminary ichnological analysis focusing on characterization of ichnofabrics during the MPT, to evaluate the incidence of atmosphere/ocean changes on macrobenthic tracemaker community. Four main ichnofabrics have been differentiated, showing an increase in bioturbation intensity: a) non-bioturbated ichnofabric, characterized by the absence of biogenic structures (ii 1); b) overprinted ichnofabric, identified by the near absence of in-situ bioturbation, but the presence of some overprinting discrete trace fossils, such as *Thalassinoides* (ii 2); c) diverse ichnofabric, showing the higher comparative diversity of in-situ trace fossils (i.e., *Planolites*, *Scolicia*, *Zoophycos*; ii 3-4) and; d) mono-specific ichnofabric, revealing a total bioturbation texture (ii 5) by dominance/exclusiveness of *Scolicia*. Stratigraphic analysis of ichnofabrics reveals a variable distribution, with alternance, at a variable scale, of mono-specific, diverse, and overprinted ichnofabrics, punctuated by the record of non-bioturbated ichnofabric. Preliminary interpretation of distribution and comparative abundance of ichnofabrics reveals the role of oxygenation and organic matter availability at the sea floor and into the substrate on macrobenthic tracemaker community in agreement with micropaleontological and total

organic carbon data. These variations can be related to ocean productivity and the dynamic of deep-sea waters.

Keywords: *ODP Site 1240; Mid-Pleistocene Transition; ichnofabric analysis; oxygenation and organic matter; ocean dynamics.*

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Ichnofabrics and paleoenvironmental changes along a contouritic drift evolution: the Spitali section (Pakhna Formation, Cyprus)

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In the last decade, ichnological analysis has been revealed as tool in the characterization of bottom current processes and facies (contourites) (Rodríguez-Tovar et al., 2022). Evolution of contouritic drift determined changes in paleoenvironmental (ecological and depositional) conditions, affecting sedimentological and ichnological features at several orders of magnitude. Miocene deep-marine deposits at Cyprus allow interpretation of bottom currents related to the evolution of the nearby Indian Gateway (Hernández-Molina et al., 2022). Here we present a preliminary ichnofabric analysis conducted in the Spitali section (Pakhna Formation, Cyprus) to evaluate paleoenvironmental changes during evolution of one Miocene drift.

The carbonate succession studied at the Spitali road cut is about 140 m thick and formed during the late Burdigalian/Langhian to Tortonian at the southern continental slope of Cyprus (Davies, 2001). The lower and middle part of the succession mainly consists of decimetre- to metre-thick bigradational sequences of mud- to sand-sized bioclastic contourites, which are interbedded with hemipelagic/pelagic deposits and abundant turbidites and reworked turbidites together with a few debrites. The succession of contourite sequences frequently include base-cut- and top-cut-out sequences. In the middle part of the succession, the contourite deposits are more mud-rich and form thinner sequences, while in the upper part of the succession they are almost absent and pelagites/hemipelagites prevail. This vertical sedimentary stacking pattern records the long-term upslope migration of the drift.

Trace fossil assemblage can be assigned to the *Cruziana* ichnofacies and probably *Zoophycos* ichnofacies. Significant variations in ichnological properties (i.e., ichnodiversity, ichnofabric index, cross-cutting relationships) are observed through the section, as revealed in the registered ichnofabrics. At the outcrop scale, three main ichnofabrics have been differentiated from bottom to top of the section. The lower part of the section is identified by an ichnofabric characterized by the absence/scarcity of discrete traces (ii 1-2) with dominant vertical structures, showing scarce cross-cutting relationships. In the middle part, a thin interval is differentiated by an ichnofabric dominated by *Zoophycos*, showing the highest abundance of

traces (ii 3-5), with vertical and horizontal structures (i.e., *Palaeophycos*, *Planolites*, *Thalassinoides*), and cross-cutting relationships. The upper part of the section shows an ichnofabric with moderate/abundant (ii 3-4) vertical and horizontal traces (i.e., *Planolites*, *Thalassinoides*) but the absence of *Zoophycos*. In this general trend, minor variations can be observed between beds, irrespective of the dominant ichnofabric.

Observed variations are interpreted as revealing favorable environmental conditions for trace maker community in terms of oxygenation and benthic food availability, but significant changes in hydrodynamic energy and rate of sedimentation because the long-term drift evolution influencing tracemakers and determining ichnofabric differentiation and distribution.

Keywords: *contouritic drift; Miocene; Cyprus; ichnofabric approach; paleoenvironment.*

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***Oravaichnium-Lockeia* ichnofabric: A favourable feeding scenario for osteostracid fishes (Lower Devonian, Cantabrian Cordillera, N Spain)**

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The studied material is located east of the Molín del Puerto beach (Gozón municipality, Asturias, N Spain). The rocks outcropping around this area belong to the Cantabrian Zone, and are assigned to the Lower Devonian aged Rañeces Group, which is interpreted as deposited on the continental shelf of western Gondwana between the Lochkovian and Emsian stages. The Rañeces Group is made up of four lithostratigraphic units, the Nieva, Bañugues, La Ladróna and Aguión formations, with the studied section belonging to the Nieva Formation, Lochkovian in age at its base to Pragian at its top. It is composed mainly of bioclastic carbonates and shales, interpreted as deposited in an outer carbonate ramp environment affected by storm events. The section is three-meter thick, and consists of alternating bioturbated, fine-grained bioclastic limestone beds with hummocky cross-stratification with pink/grey shales and some thin lumachellic limestones, which are dominant towards the base. Ichnofossils can be found across the entire section but are more abundant on the fine-grained limestones.

The ichnofabric is represented by resting and locomotion structures of infaunal bivalves, specifically, by *Lockeia siliquaria* James, 1879 and *Oravaichnium hrabei* Plička and Uhrová, 1990. *Lockeia siliquaria* is preserved as epichnial concave semirelief that forms small, elongated depressions ranging from 2.2 to 18 mm in length (average value 52 mm) and from 0.3 to 8 mm in width and up to 10 mm in depth. Both ends can be pointed, or one of them is much more rounded and wider than the opposite. Occasionally, they are filled with the same material as the bedrock, reflecting the internal cast of the producer. They can appear isolated or in more or less oriented groups.

Oravaichnium hrabei exhibits the same type of preservation, consisting of grooves that are straight to irregularly sinuous, curved, or meandering. The length varies between 3.4 and 283.3 mm (average value 29.1 mm) and has an almost constant width of between 1 and 22.7 mm (average of 2.5 mm). They often appear in parallel groups or in radial arrangements. Commonly, they are filled with material from the host rock or even from the overlying layer. In these cases, the cross-section of the fill is subrectangular, not ridged, with slightly rounded edges. On the margins of the burrows, a much finer-grained material is observed in places,

which has generally detached, leaving a very narrow fine groove on each side. Commonly, *Oravaichnium* is connected at one end to *Lockeia*, even to the cast of the producing bivalve. A series of sub-rectangular depressions are also found, with an average size of 10.5 x 6 cm. Their profile is asymmetric, with a slightly inclined entrance ramp at the back and a deeper part (1.8 cm on average) towards the exit or front area. More than 50% of these depressions are oriented parallel to the paleocurrent direction (N 253° E) and are closely associated with the burrows produced by the bivalves (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Plan view of the surface with small dunes showing the subrectangular depressions (white arrows) attributed to feeding by *Cephalaspis* and the locomotion-resting traces by bivalves. Or: *Oravaichnium*, Lo: *Lockeia*. Scale of the bar: 5 cm.

Given this shallow marine context of a surface highly bioturbated by bivalves, the most likely producer for these depressions must be an osteostracid fish, similar to *Cephalaspis*. This fish had its mouth located just beneath its head and fed on the bottom by moving its head from side to side. This way, it could easily disturb the sediment, digging up bivalves or even detritus buried on the sea floor.

Keywords: *infaunal bioturbation; bivalves; osteostracid; Cephalaspis; Lower Devonian.*

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Trace fossils from Upper Triassic Exter Formation, SW Germany

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The Exter Formation (“Rhätsandstein”) of the SW Germanic Basin have been interpreted to represent the dynamic interplay between terrestrial and marine environments during the Rhaetian stage (Late Triassic). While valued as a frost-resistant building material and widely used as a local building stone, its trace fossil assemblages remain largely underexplored. Reported trace fossils from the Rhätsandstein include *Diplocraterion*, *Asteriacites*, *Solemyatuba*, and rhizoliths. This study investigates the trace fossils of the Rhätsandstein and their paleoenvironmental implications. Preliminary fieldwork has been conducted at a quarry (“am Steinbruchweg”) near Pfrondorf, Tübingen, Germany where trace fossils are described in situ. Trace fossil characterization is based on classic ichnotaxobases, and the degree of bioturbation was classified on a scale from 1 (0–20%) to 5 (80–100%). The quarry exposes approximately 7 m of fine- to medium-grained, lenticular to tabular, well-sorted quartz sandstones. These sandstones occasionally exhibit low-angle cross-stratification and localized current or wave ripples. Thin-bedded pelitic layers are rare and occur between sandstone beds. Trace fossils were identified at three stratigraphic levels. The assemblage is dominated by U-shaped burrows, with or without spreiten, identified as *Diplocraterion* and *Arenicolites*, respectively. Simple vertical burrows, identified as *Skolithos*, are also common. Additionally, burrows observed on some bedding planes, were identified as *Palaeophycus* and *Lockeia*. The recurrence of protrusive spreiten structures (Fig. 1B-C) attributed to *Diplocraterion* suggests high sedimentation rates, likely associated with a deltaic depositional setting. The overall low ichnodiversity supports an interpretation of a stressed depositional environment, with evidence of marine conditions indicated by rare molds of *Rhaetavicula contorta*. While this sandstone has been variously as representing partially exposed beach deposits (e.g., Aepler, 1974) within in a deltaic setting, the ichnocoenosis described here aligns more closely with submarine conditions.

Keywords: delta; applied ichnology; ichnofabric approach; Triassic.

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Fig. 1: Trace fossils from studied outcrop. A. Geologic log and general view of the studied section. B-C. Details of *Diplocraterion*; D-E. Detail of dense bioturbated intervals, dominated by *Skolithos*. F. Example of *Arenicolites*; note the absence of a basal ramification, precluding attribution to *Solemyatuba*. G. Bedding plane view of *Diplocraterion*, *Skolithos*, and *Palaeophycus*.

***Skolithos* piperock from the Lower Devonian storm beds**

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Skolithos piperock is prevalent in Cambrian shallow marine deposits but diminishes throughout the Paleozoic. This study reports an interval with *Skolithos* piperock from the upper Furnas Formation (Lower Devonian, Paraná Basin, Brazil), offering insights into the paleoenvironmental interpretation of nearshore sandstones. The studied section comprises eight sedimentary facies (1 medium-grained sandstone with low-angle, 2 planar, or 3 trough cross-stratification, corresponding to foreshore [1 and 2] to upper shoreface [3] settings; 4 very fine to fine-grained sandstone with wave cross lamination or 5 hummocky cross-stratification, corresponding to lower shoreface [4] to transitional offshore [5] settings; 6 massive very fine- to coarse-grained sandstones corresponding to lower shoreface to transitional offshore, 7 siltstone with parallel lamination, and 8 mudstone, both corresponding to offshore settings). The vertical stacking pattern shows a 3rd-order transgressive pattern, evidenced by transition from sandstone-dominated intervals indicative of nearshore environments to siltstone and mudstone facies representing lower energy offshore conditions. The trace fossil assemblage consists of six ichnocoenoses: *Macaronichnus*, *Skolithos*, *Asterosoma*, *Rosselia*, *Rhizocorallium*, and *Phycosiphon* ichnocoenoses, reflecting a proximal-to-distal gradient. The *Macaronichnus* and *Skolithos* ichnocoenoses characterize high-energy nearshore environments. The *Asterosoma* and *Rosselia* ichnocoenoses indicate reduced sedimentation rates in transitional offshore. The *Rhizocorallium* and *Phycosiphon* ichnocoenoses represent lower-energy offshore environment. A stratigraphic shift from a highly bioturbated *Skolithos* ichnocoenosis to an *Asterosoma* ichnocoenosis occurs at 14 m within a 76 m-thick section, marking the transition from a high-energy shoreface to a more stable, lower-energy environment. This change reflects a transgressive trend between the Furnas and Ponta Grossa formations (Lower Devonian). *Skolithos* piperock is interpreted as the result of multiple storm-driven erosional processes, leading to a time-averaged ichnocoenosis. Basin-scale correlations of *Skolithos* piperock are supported by this occurrence in the Paraná Basin and equivalent transgressive deposits in Bolivia, where similar trace fossil distributions are observed. The high

density of *Skolithos* burrows, as piperock, suggests a taphonomic bias, wherein deeper *Skolithos* burrows are preferentially preserved while shallower structures are removed by erosion. This bias, coupled with opportunistic recolonization following storm events, enhances the preservation potential of *Skolithos* as piperock and reinforces its utility as a regional stratigraphic marker.

Keywords: trace fossils, Ponta Grossa Formation, Furnas Formation, storm beds, transgressive systems tract.

Funding/Acknowledgement: Alexander von Humboldt Foundation/CAPES; FAPERJ; FAPESP.

Fig. 1. *Skolithos* piperock in studied outcrop. A. Vertical view of the *Skolithos* piperock. B. Sketch of fig. A highlighting the successive erosive surfaces and the presence of *Skolithos* crossing beds. C. Plane view of dense *Skolithos* piperock. D. Inclined view of *Skolithos* piperock. E–F. Vertical view of *Skolithos* piperock; white dashed line highlighting the erosive surface, separating eroded *Skolithos* as well as *Skolithos* crossing beds. Scale bars = 2 cm.

Trace fossil analysis in Paleogene braided river system from Volta Redonda Basin, Continental Rift of Southeastern Brazil

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Trace fossils serve as valuable indicators for paleoecological and paleoenvironmental research, recording organism behavior influenced by environmental parameters. However, trace fossils within braided river systems are rarely investigated worldwide. Despite the growing interest in ichnological studies within the Continental Rift of Southeastern Brazil, there remains a notable scarcity of research focusing on integrated ichno-sedimentological analysis. This study analyzes ichnological data from the Volta Redonda Basin, focusing on two subsurface logs to provide paleoenvironmental interpretations. Core samples were examined for sedimentary facies, revealing four distinct facies within the Resende Formation, related to unidirectional tractive flows and overbank deposits of a braided depositional paleoenvironment. The ichnocoenosis included *Skolithos*, *Beaconites*, and a crustacean burrow, with *Skolithos* ichnocoenosis being the most recurrent. The results indicate that the Volta Redonda Basin experienced diverse depositional conditions characterized by dominant high-energy levels, while the presence of rhizohaloes in low-energy deposits suggests short periods of subaerial exposure. The dominance of *Skolithos* ichnofacies in the few bioturbated levels demonstrated that high-energy conditions were a barrier to intense colonization of the substrate, with sparse signatures of *Scoyenia* ichnofacies being very restricted in the studied sections.

Keywords: Beaconites, Taenidium, crustacean burrow, rhizohaloes, Rift Basin.

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Fig. 1: Paleoenvironmental reconstruction of the Resende Formation in Volta Redonda Basin.

Continental trace fossil analysis and the marine paradox in Areado Group, Sanfranciscana Basin

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Ichnological analyses coupled with sedimentary facies description and interpretation are widely used to reconstruct depositional environments. In this study, ichnological and sedimentological data were integrated for the mostly continental Areado Group (Lower Cretaceous, Sanfranciscana Basin, Brazil), from where a marine influence has been recently suggested based on the presence of marine microfossils in the Três Barras Formation. In this scenario, the trace fossils characterization of the Areado Group allows to infer paleoenvironmental variations and helps to test the hypothesis of the putative marine influence. Despite rich macrofossils, including fish, dinosaurs, and ostracods, the ichnological record of this unit remains poorly understood. The trace fossil analysis presented was conducted in the Morro do Cruzeiro section, where marine microfossils were recovered, and in surrounding areas (from João Pinheiro to Carmo do Paranaíba municipalities, Minas Gerais State, SE Brazil). Among the three lithostratigraphic units analyzed, the lowermost conglomeratic Abaeté Formation lacks trace fossils, while the intermediate Quiricó Formation contains sparse occurrences of *Planolites*, *Skolithos*, *Taenidium*, and vertebrate burrows. The uppermost Três Barras Formation also preserves *Planolites*, *Skolithos*, and *Taenidium*, along with *Palaeophycus*, *Beaconites*, rhizoliths, and diroturbations. The bioturbation index for the Quiricó Formation is low (BI 1-2), while for the Três Barras Formation, it ranges from low to moderate (BI 1-3). These ichnoassemblages align with the *Scoyenia* ichnofacies, suggesting no evidence of marine influence in the studied interval. These findings indicate that the marine microfossils may result from punctual, short-lived marine incursions or high-magnitude ephemeral events, such as sandstorms transporting marine fine-grained sediment that left no records beyond reworked/redeposited fine-grained sediments and microfossils, including mm- to µm-scale bioclasts.

Keywords: *ichnofacies; applied ichnology; continental deposits; Cretaceous.*

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Fig. 1. Trace fossils from studied interval. A-B. Trace fossils from Quiricó Formation; C-F. Trace fossils from Três Barras Formation; note rhizoliths in F, G, Paleoburrow attributed to lungfish or a small lizard. H. Dinosaur burrow from Três Barras Formation with its schematic draw. Sk = Skolithos, Pa = Palaeophycus, Ta = Taenidium, Pl = Planolites.

Modern *Macaronichnus* burrow on a sandy beach in New South Wales, Australia

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The trace fossil *Macaronichnus segregatis* is an intrastratal burrow in fine- to medium-grained sandy marine deposits. Many studies have utilized this trace fossil as an indicator of the foreshore environment (Seike, 2007). Recently, this trace fossil has also been used as a proxy for cold water, such as beaches in high latitudes or those affected by coastal upwelling (Quiroz et al., 2019). The modern analog of *M. segregatis* is feeding traces of the opheliid worm *Thoracophelia* spp. Although neoichnology of the worm burrow has provided useful paleoecological insights on the trace fossils, modern analogs of *M. segregatis* have only been reported from the northern hemisphere to date.

We recently found the modern *M. segregatis* burrow from the southern hemisphere. The burrow occurred on a sandy beach in New South Wales, Australia, and was seen only at the mid-foreshore level. The producer of the structure was the opheliid worm *Thoracophelia* sp. The burrow's dominant orientation was horizontal, the same as for equivalent burrows in the northern hemisphere. Because the *Thoracophelia* worm is known to inhabit worldwide, its feeding trace, the modern analog of the *M. segregatis*, could also occur throughout the world. Our finding of the modern *M. segregatis* from the southern hemisphere can reinforce the paleoenvironmental utility of the trace fossil as a sea level (foreshore environment) indicator although some larger ichnosubspecies of *Macaronichnus segregatis*, *M. s. degiberti* occurs in deeper environments (Seike et al. 2011; Miguez-Salas, O., et al., 2020).

Keywords: neoichnology; sandy beach; foreshore; worm; polychaete.

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Modern analog of sequestrichnia: shrimp burrows stuffed with seagrass leaves

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Sequestrichnia are trace fossil structures constructed for food storage or stowing activity. Investigating modern analogs of sequestrichnia is important for our understanding of the trace fossils (Curran et al., in review). In this presentation, we will show modern shrimp burrows having chambers stuffed with seagrass leaves.

The callichirid shrimp *Neocallichirus grandimana*, and *N. maryae* inhabit tidal flats and shallow subtidal sandy bottoms on San Salvador Island, Bahamas. The morphology of *N. grandimana* burrow consists of horizontally-branched tunnels with knob-like termini or chamber structures commonly stuffed with vegetative matter. *Neocallichirus maryae* has a burrow that is U-shaped and has numerous small chambers. Although the burrows of both species have sequestrichnia structures as part of their burrows, our stable isotope analysis revealed that the food sources for each species are different: the most important food source for both species is the same, but the second most important food source differs between them (Seike and Curran, 2023). This suggests that we need to know what is stored in the sequestrichnia structures to understand them fully.

The strahlaxiid shrimp *Neaxius acanthus* inhabits a gravelly intertidal flat in southwestern Japan. The burrow had a single aperture, a vertical shaft, and chambers at the bottom. Many seagrass leaves are stored in the burrow chamber. We conducted an X-ray CT scanning of the *N. acanthus* burrow cast, which revealed that the burrow had many burrow associates, including a galeommatoidean bivalve and a phenacolepadid gastropod in the chamber (Seike and Goto, 2017). This finding suggests that sequestrichnia are important not only as storage space for burrow producers, but also as microhabitats for the tiny burrow associates that inhabit these chambers.

Keywords: *neoichnology; burrow; seagrass; shrimp; sequestrichnia.*

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Utility of trace fossils for the identification of climatic and ocean-bottom conditions during the Eocene-Oligocene Transition (EOT): IODP Expeditions 390 & 393

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The Eocene-Oligocene Transition (EOT) marks the shift in global climate from the hothouse of the early Cenozoic (~34 Ma) to the icehouse conditions present today (Koeberl and Montanari, 2009). This transition is characterized by significant environmental changes, including Antarctic glaciation, altered ocean circulation, and reduced sea levels (Goldner et al., 2014; Dutkiewicz and Muller, 2022; Straume et al., 2022). Despite its importance, the EOT's dynamics and response of benthic community to climate and oceanic bottom conditions remain underexplored due to the scarcity of well-preserved sedimentary records and hemispherical differences in cooling trends (Prothero and Emry, 1996; Maravelis and Zelilidis, 2012; Abelson and Erez, 2017). This study scrutinizes trace fossils from sediment cores retrieved across the western flank of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge during the International Ocean Discovery Program (IODP) Expeditions 390 and 393. Sediment cores from sites U1558 and U1556, located approximately 1067 and 1250 km west of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge at depths of 4334 m and 5002 m, respectively, provide a unique opportunity to examine mid-latitude paleoclimate and paleoceanographic conditions during the EOT. This research focuses on trace fossils as proxies for environmental parameters, such as oxygen levels, sedimentation rates, organic matter availability, and seafloor hydraulic energy. Using trace-fossil diversity, composition, tiering, and distribution, bulk stable isotopes, and X-Ray Fluorescence scanning, this study correlates bioturbation patterns with broader paleoenvironmental changes. Data for this project were retrieved from the JOIDES Resolution Science Operator online database. Enhanced imagery processing techniques, including Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (Miguez-Salas et al., 2019), were applied to core photographs to improve low sediment contrast and trace fossil visibility. Study findings reveal a decline in bioturbation levels during the EOT, evidenced by a reduction in trace fossil size, complexity, and ichnodiversity, with *Chondrites* often being the only ichnotaxa evident. This decline aligns with increased sediment reflectance, indicating more calcareous and less terrigenous material, likely linked to shifts in ocean productivity, terrigenous input, and/or carbonate compensation depth. Environmental stressors, such as reduced organic matter availability, lower temperatures, and changes in ocean

circulation, likely contributed to the diminished ecological complexity of benthic communities. Changes in ocean circulation due to the formation of deep-water masses around Antarctica (Lefebvre et al., 2012; Thompson et al., 2021) and introduction of cooler waters likely reduced primary productivity in surface waters, leading to less organic material sinking to the seafloor, which in turn would have affected the food supply for benthic organisms (Savrda and Bottjer, 1986; Uchman and Wetzel, 2011). This reduction in food availability could explain, in part, the decline in both the abundance and diversity of trace fossils during this period. This research enhances understanding of the EOT's impact on marine benthic ecosystems and highlights the importance of ichnological data in reconstructing past climates.

Keywords: *palaeoenvironment; applied ichnology; International Ocean Discovery Program; deep ocean; Eocene-Oligocene Transition.*

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Ichnofabrics and ichnology of storm beds of the lower Cambrian of the Holy Cross Mountains (Poland)

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Lower Cambrian shallow-water siliciclasticss from the Holy Cross Mts. contain a rich assemblage of trace fossils and exhibit varying degrees of bioturbation. The shales of the Czarna and Kamieniec formations, deposited in an offshore, are almost unbioturbated. Weak bioturbation is mainly caused by *Planolites*, with occasional occurrences of *Bergaueria* or *Treptichnus*. Thin intercalations of rippled sandstone beds is interpreted as distal tempestites. The Ociesęki Formation is bipartite. Its lower part, deposited in a lower shoreface, features thin, highly bioturbated sandstones interbedded with unbioturbated, horizontally or ripple-laminated beds. Many beds consist of thin layers of unbioturbated sediment embedded within totally bioturbated deposits. These unbioturbated layers are interpreted as distal tempestites. Ichnofabric is difficult to discern because the heavily bioturbated sediment typically lacks recognisable trace fossils, the most abundant of which are *Planolites* and *Teichichnus*. In the intergrading zone between sandy and silty facies (Kamieniec Fm), thin wacke beds dominate, exhibiting varying degrees of bioturbation, almost exclusively caused by *Teichichnus*. The upper part of the Ociesęki Formation, deposited in a middle shoreface, contains medium and thick sandstone beds with *Arenicolites* and *Skolithos* (up to 30 cm deep) ichnofabric, with *Diplocraterion* occurring at slightly shallower depths. Some unbioturbated beds display ripple laminations and hummocky cross-stratification, which are interpreted as proximal tempestites. The studied formations reveal numerous tempestites, often preserved only as very thin layers of partly bioturbated sandstones. The presence of very thin tempestites results from the absence of benthic organisms in deeper marine zones during the Cambrian and the deep penetration of sediment occurring only in shallow zones. Unbioturbated, rippled beds document that storm-deposited sand buried the bottom-dwelling population, which only recovered under low-energy environmental conditions. Very shallow bioturbation of lower shoreface tempestites is typical of the early Palaeozoic, when worms were the primary sediment-penetrating organisms. Between storms, at low sedimentation rates, the deposits were almost completely bioturbated. In the shoreface zone, storms were thus a limiting factor for the development of benthic communities and bioturbation. In contrast, in the offshore zone, they facilitated the colonisation of areas otherwise unfavourable for life.

Keywords: *trace fossils; bioturbation; shallow water marine deposition.*

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Ichnofabrics controlled by transgressive-regressive regimes in marine Neogene deposits from Gran Canaria, Canary Islands, Spain

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The fan delta deposits of the Las Palmas Detritic Formation (Mio–Pliocene), Gran Canaria, sandwiched between volcanic rocks, are dominated by conglomerates and breccias (Schneider, 2004). However, they also include calcareous sandstones, which represent a transgressive-regressive cycle related with a relative sea level change. The ichnology of the sandstones in the Las Cuevas de Guincho section was reported by Mayoral et al. (2019), who identified a distinct and abrupt transition up the section from an *Ophiomorpha nodosa*-dominated assemblage to a *Bichordites monastiriensis*-dominated assemblage of trace fossils, with some contribution of *Rosselia socialis* and *Macaronichnus segregatis*, within a ca. 7 m-thick unit 3 of Schneider et al. (2004). These assemblages were attributed to the *Skolithos* and the proximal *Cruziana* ichnofacies, respectively, and were interpreted as reflecting an energy shift from the upper-middle shoreface to the lower shoreface, consistent with the ichnofacies framework.

While not overlooking the change in energy indicated by the ichnofacies, the significant shift in ichnofabric is linked to sediment dynamics influencing tracemakers within a transgressive-regressive cycle (Fig. 1). During the transgressive regime, sedimentation was concentrated nearshore, migrating onshore as the shoreline advanced landward. Consequently, the rate of sedimentation was low, and the sea floor was relatively stable in the upper-middle shoreface, creating conditions favourable for colonisation by shrimps producing *Ophiomorpha*, which were capable of maintaining their open burrows.

In contrast, during the regressive phase, sediments prograded rapidly towards the offshore, accompanied by a much higher sedimentation rate and increased erosional disturbances. Under these conditions, shrimps were unable to sustain their burrows and were replaced by irregular echinoids, which produced *Bichordites*. The echinoids could burrow in shifting sediments without maintaining a permanent connection to the sea floor, making them more resilient to the higher sediment dynamics than decapod crustaceans.

This scenario suggests that the change in ichnofabrics was not driven by bathymetric shifts but rather by sediment dynamics, leading to community replacement where shrimps were supplanted by echinoids. It is also possible that amensalism contributed to this replacement, as the horizontal burrowing activity of echinoids may have damaged the vertical open burrows of shrimps.

Keywords: *palaeoenvironment; fan delta, Bichordites, Ophiomorpha; Pliocene.*

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Fig. 1. Distribution of ichnofabrics in unit 3 of the Las Cuevas de Guincho section of the Las Palmas Detritic Formation (Mio-Pliocene), Gran Canaria, Canary Islands, Spain.

Quantitative insights into Ediacaran locomotory trace fossils: evidence of slender A–P body plans and their role in early ecosystem interactions

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Trace fossils are invaluable resources for studying early animals and their co-evolution with palaeoenvironments, especially during the Proterozoic–Cambrian transition. While the Cambrian Explosion is believed to have been driven by the emergence of eumetazoans with distinct body axes, the incomplete and patchy body fossil record has often left locomotory trace fossils as the primary source of anatomical information on these trace-makers. But identifying conclusive evidence of a slender eumetazoan anterior–posterior (A–P) axis from these Proterozoic organism–substrate interactions has long been challenging and remains quantitatively underexplored. In this study, we utilize the integral scale—representing the distance over which the trajectory (i.e., force and displacement at the organism–substrate interface) is self-correlated—as an indicator of the characteristic length of locomotory structures of the trace-maker. Analyzing trajectories preserved simultaneously with trace-makers in both fossil records and modern observations, we identify the proportionality between the normalized characteristic locomotory length and integral scale across deep time. Applying this scaling law to terminal Proterozoic trace fossils, we reveal their normalized characteristic lengths of 5–8. The minimal body lengths of the trace-makers would have exceeded this range, therefore evidencing the existence of slender A–P axes in these early bilaterians, likely with rigid, hydrostatic bodies reinforced by robust nerve–muscle systems. These adaptations would have greatly enhanced directional sensation, locomotion, and environmental exploration, enabling these organisms to thrive in dynamically complex, heterogeneous, and shifting habitats. Such features facilitated niche partitioning and provided access to wider ecospace, setting the stage for occupation of shallow marine settings. Our findings suggest a deeper and well-equipped evolutionary root for the Cambrian Explosion and Cambrian Substrate Revolution and establish a novel, quantitative framework for the study of deep-time trace fossils, offering robust insights into early animal anatomy and palaeoecological interactions.

Keywords: trace fossil; integral scale; uniformitarianism; early animal; Ediacaran–Cambrian transition.

Changes in trace-fossil distribution in the transition from a wave-dominated shallow-marine platform to a delta complex: the Devonian Gualilán Group of the Argentine Precordillera

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Shallow-marine systems are sensitive to changes commonly resulting from fluvial input, such as sedimentation rate and food supply. Outcrops of middle Paleozoic shallow-marine siliciclastic rocks of the Gualilán Group in the Central Precordillera of western Argentina allow an evaluation of changes in trace-fossil distribution in response to environmental factors. This unit comprises the Talacasto (Lochkovian–late Pragian) and Punta Negra formations (late Pragian–?Eifelian). At the Lomas de Los Piojos section, the Talacasto Formation consists of greenish-gray, highly bioturbated, mixed silty-very fine-grained sandstone with very fine-grained sandstone intercalations accumulated in a wave-dominated shallow-marine environment. Two trace fossil assemblages were recognized, with full-relief and epichnial preservation. (1) The dominant *Zoophycos-Phycosiphon* assemblage, comprising *Zoophycos* isp., *Phycosiphon incertum*, subordinate *Nereites missouriensis*, and *Chondrites* isp., is preserved in mixed silty sandstone, reflecting calm energy conditions, limited food availability, and a shallow redox boundary within the substrate. (2) the sparsely distributed *Rosselia* assemblage, including *Rosselia socialis*, *Skolithos* isp., and *Arenicolites* isp., is associated with hummocky cross-stratified very fine-grained sandstone intercalations at the uppermost interval, indicating episodic higher-energy conditions and organic particles in suspension in the water column due to stronger influence of storms. The passage from the Talacasto Formation to the Punta Negra Formation is transitional. The Punta Negra Formation is characterized by a sharp decline in body fossils and an increase in plant fossils (*Sporogonites*, *Cyclostigma*, *Isidrophyton*, *Haplostigma*). The unit starts with sparsely bioturbated dark green mudstone passing upwards to erosively based amalgamated hummocky cross-stratified sandstone, suggesting a progradational stacking pattern and a shift to a wave-dominated deltaic

depositional system. Hypichnial trace fossils are dominant, including *Helminthoidichnites tenuis*, *?Helminthopsis abeli*, *Circulichnis* isp., *Palaeophycus tubularis*, and plug-shaped burrows (*?Bergaueria* isp.). Non-specialized grazing trails in the Punta Negra Formation may reflect increased food supply due proximity to a delta. Integration of ichnologic, sedimentologic, and stratigraphic datasets refines our understanding of the depositional evolution in the Precordillera Basin during the middle Paleozoic.

Keywords: *Gondwana; Paleozoic; paleoecology; ecological factors; depositional system.*

Ichnofabrics without trace fossils – interpretation and significance of biodeformational structures

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Animals moving on or burrowing through the substrate disturb and mix the originally layered sediment record while producing bioturbational sedimentary structures. Since the bioturbating benthos responds to the ecological conditions, a systematic analysis of the produced traces and their assemblages (= ichnocoenoses) in combination with the sedimentary facies is suitable to decipher previous environmental settings, subsumed in the ichnofacies and the ichnofabric concept. The backbone of both are trace fossils, which, however, represent only part of the bioturbational record. Based on extensive experimental studies in aquarium, Schäfer (1956) recognized that many animals only disturb pre-existing structures and he suggested to distinguish (1) traces (trace fossils; ‘fossitextura figurativa’), which have distinct outlines and a recurrent morphology allowing an ichnotaxonomic classification, and (2) biodeformational structures (‘fossitextura deformativa’), which are manifested as (a) localized layer-bending encompassing one or many laminae or (b) complete de-layering (homogenization) of a sediment volume. In the North Sea, biodeformational structures were found to coin about 50% of the sediment fabric (Schäfer, 1962). Since biodeformational structures do not exhibit typical features, they were dealt with only subordinately. Obviously, generation of biodeformational structures requires a loose, soupy, or soft substrate, otherwise animals produce distinct traces (e.g., Wetzel and Uchman, 1998; Goldring, 1995).

Biodeformational structures occur in various substrates or environments and, therefore, they are suggested to be classified according to their size, two general types are distinguished, (1) sub-macroscopic features, so-called cryptichnia, which result from cryptobioturbation, and (2) macroscopic features, so-called ‘deformichnia’.

Subcategories of these two general types are related to specific substrate and environmental settings. In detail the following classes are suggested.

1. Cryptichnia

(a) Surface mixed layer with ‘cryptichnia var. mixta’. They are formed in oxygenated sediments, which accumulate at rates >2–5 cm/kyr. In such deposits, sufficient organic matter (= benthic food) is commonly embedded for nutrition.

- (b) Homogeneous oceanic red beds with ‘cryptichnia var. rubra’. They are formed in sediments, which accumulate at rates <math><2-5\text{ cm/kyr}</math> and thus, are limited in benthic food (e.g., Wetzel and Uchman, 2018). This leads – on the long term due to evolution – to a miniaturization of the burrowing fauna (e.g., Gage and Tyler, 1991).
- (c) Homogeneous “black mud” with ‘cryptichnia var. atra’. They are formed under anaerobic to dysaerobic conditions. During re-oxygenation, small fauna has a pioneering role to make the substrate hospitable for successive organisms by intense bioirrigation. Observations in modern settings show that the onset of cryptobioturbation is not related to a specific oxygen level.

2. Deformichnia

2.1 Deformichnia in soupy to soft substrate

- (a) Navichnia. In soupy substrate, animals need to swim through the substrate. The resultant structures were called according to their appearance “mantle and swirl” traces (Lobza and Schieber, 1999). Later the name navichnia was suggested (Gingras et al., 2007).
- (b) Turbichnia. Is there a strong consistency contrast between burrow fill and host sediment, during compaction, burrow fill and margins become so intensely deformed and squeezed into the host sediment that an ichnotaxonomic classification is no longer possible. Such structures were termed turbichnia by Leszczyński (2004). In addition, also the inverse case, grainy sediment filling a burrow emplaced in soft mud may lead to such deformations.

2.2 Deformichnia in loose or soft substrate

- (a) ‘Permischichnia’ (eddy-like sediment disturbance). In sandy or muddy substrate, in particular in shallow-marine settings, many sediment-feeding animals respond to changes of the available benthic food by adapting their ingestion rate (e.g., Cammen, 1980). In many instances, biodeformation structures are produced, which have an eddy-like appearance. In the North Sea, about 50% of the sediment are churned by such structures (Schäfer, 1962). Also in upwelling areas, permischichnia are formed because these sediments are organic-rich making a behavioral specialization for nutrition superfluous (Wetzel, 1981).
- (b) ‘Cribellichnia’ (biostratification). In sediment composed of a wide grain-size spectrum dense populations of animals only ingest fine grains, like *Arenicola*, while not-ingested coarse material becomes enriched underneath the bioturbated interval (e.g., Schäfer, 1962).
- (c) Fugichnia. Due to severe, depositional or erosional events, animals burrow “in panic” up- or downward, respectively, and deform laminae (if present), which continue into the

surrounding sediment. Such traces have no sharp outlines that would allow an ichnotaxonomic classification.

- (d) ‘Equilibrichnia deformativa’. Animals move up- or downward due to not-too-rapid deposition or erosion. If no distinct traces are left, the produced burrows represent biodeformational structures to be classified as equilibrichnia deformativa.

Keywords: *Biodeformational structures; cryptobioturbation; navichnia; fugichnia.*

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